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in Conjunction with Real Measurements

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DELIVERABLE D1: Good Practice Guide on Uncertainty Evaluation for Virtual Experiments in Conjunction with Real Measurements

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1. Introduction

Following the digital transformation of society, virtual experiments (VEs) are attracting substantial attention in the metrological community. Virtual metrology is listed as a key area in the strategic research agenda of EURAMET's European Metrology Network Mathmet [15] and VEs are key enabling technologies to achieve and realise European strategic policies devoted to sustainability and digitalisation within the complex framework of Industry 4.0 and the European Green Deal.

The introduction of a virtual representation of a real measurement requires a considerable complexity, in particular for highly accurate and precise measurement systems in metrology. The advantage of such an approach is that real measurements, which can be costly to perform or even impossible to repeat under fixed conditions, can be amended by virtual measurements to analyse properties of the underlying quantities. A prominent challenge in metrology that can benefit from the advances in virtual metrology is uncertainty evaluation. Uncertainty evaluation involving VEs is an important area of research, since the practical combination of real measurements with a virtual- or digital representation of a measurement may depend on the application at hand and several scenarios are currently not treated in guidance documents on uncertainty evaluation in measurement. Recent work in this regard considers uncertainty evaluation for the applications of, e.g., coordinate measuring machines [5, 70, 31, 48], tilted-wave interferometry [20, 19], flow simulations [68, 77] and virtual scatterometry [26, 47]. Some more theoretically oriented papers [80, 33, 55] also consider compliance and equivalence under certain conditions with the Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (GUM) [42] and its supplements JCGM-101 [41] and JCGM-102 [43].

1.1. What to expect from this Good Practice Guide?

The aim of this Good Practice Guide (GPG) is to describe how to carry out uncertainty evaluation when there are real measurements available in conjunction with a VE, which models the measurement in a virtual environment. Several methods for uncertainty evaluation are presented and assessed in terms of their properties and limitations. These methods include approaches as documented in the GUM and its supplements, as well as alternative Monte Carlo sampling approaches and methods involving Bayesian inference. These methods will be applied and discussed in terms of three real measurement use cases.

To properly discuss uncertainty evaluation involving VEs in conjunction with real measurement data, the GPG will first define the term VE within the field of measurement science and metrology for this goal. The chosen definition will highlight the distinction to a Digital Twin, which, according to the ISO 30173:2023 definition [39], entails a real-time interaction in two directions between the physical world and its virtual counterpart. In an abstract sense, a VE can be considered as an integral part of a digital twin by considering its static modelling of the real measurement process. Details regarding uncertainty evaluation using digital twins are discussed in the accompanying "Good practice guide on uncertainty evaluation for digital twins" [74]. Another important aspect when employing a VE for uncertainty evaluation is the quality of the VE itself. Often, a quality assessment is performed using statistical validation techniques and reference measurements to

calibrate the VE. Following the validation, model improvements, such as advanced surrogate modelling, has to be considered. The challenges and methodologies of validation and surrogate modelling are not discussed in this GPG but will be detailed on in the also accompanying "Report on how to account for errors in the surrogate models of virtual experiments and digital twins" [75].

1.2. Real-world use cases

In this GPG, we present three examples of VEs and study in more detail how the uncertainty evaluation can be performed using these VEs.

The first example is the tilted-wave interferometer (TWI). Tilted-wave interferometry is a measurement technique for highly accurate form measurement of aspheres and freeform surfaces. The measurement system of the TWI [20, 19] combines interferometric measurements with ray tracing, perturbation methods and mathematical evaluation procedures. The measurement setup generates differently tilted wavefronts behind the collimator that illuminate the surface under test. Optical path length differences are calculated from the interferograms measured at the image detector. In order to reconstruct the form of the topography, i.e., the measurand, from this measurement data, a specific evaluation procedure is needed that requires a VE. The VE for the TWI is based on the principles of geometrical optics and implements all elements of the real measurement setup in a virtual environment, e.g., lens systems, beamsplitters, image detector, collimator, light-source, etc. Then, ray tracing and ray aiming is performed to simulate the measurement procedure. Given specific parameter values for the measurand and all other parameters involved, optical path length differences are generated by the VE that correspond to virtual replicas of the real measured optical path length differences under similar conditions assumed. In this GPG, a Bayesian inference approach developed and published in [54] is discussed. Moreover, a simplified Monte Carlo sampling approach is developed and applied to a simplified measurement setup that involves a linearization of the VE. Depending on the validity of the underlying assumptions for both uncertainty evaluation methods, recommendations for similar applications with conceptual connections to computational optical metrology will be given.

The second example regards a coordinate measuring machine (CMM). CMMs measure a cloud of 2D- or 3D-point-coordinates of an artefact and from this point-cloud shape parameters like circle diameter or circularity are evaluated. A virtual model of a CMM is usually called a VCMM and many publications have addressed this application [5, 70, 31, 48]. These publications are usually application oriented and often do not reveal all mathematical details of the underlying computations. On the contrary, in this GPG, various ways of uncertainty evaluation are formally described and applied, and the results are compared with each other. Based on the underlying assumptions of the chosen uncertainty evaluation method and the presented limitations, practical recommendations will be given.

The third example of a measurement involving a VE is simulation-aided flow rate measurement under sub-optimal circumstances (FLOW) [68, 77]. The flow dynamics are modelled by a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation which takes into account the configuration of bends upstream of the flow meter. By applying the measurement principle of the considered flow meter to the flow field

predicted by the CFD simulation, a 'virtual measurement' of the flow rate is derived. Comparing this outcome of the VE with the flow rate prescribed in the CFD simulation gives a fluid-dynamic calibration factor, with which the readings of the real flow meter can be corrected.

1.3. Structure of this document

The structure of this GPG is as follows. First in Section 2, the need of generalizing methods for uncertainty evaluation employing VEs in conjunction with real measurement data are presented in terms of challenges arising from the three use cases. Next, a formal definition of a VE and the required mathematical and statistical concepts are introduced in Section 3.1, which will be used to develop and assess the uncertainty evaluation approaches. Subsequently, an overview of several uncertainty evaluation methods is presented and underlying modelling assumptions, challenges and limitations are discussed in Section 3.2-3.4. Following the theoretical developments, appropriate uncertainty evaluation approaches for each of the use cases are presented in Sections 4, 5, and 6. This GPG ends with some recommendations for generalising practical application.

2. Challenges of uncertainty evaluation using VEs in metrological applications

VEs as an integral part of virtual metrology are fundamental in ensuring the success of modern measurement science. Several challenges arise when real measurements are combined with VEs to perform a certain measurement task. Motivated by the applications involved in the ViDiT (22DIT01) EPM project, the main challenges considered in this guide are aligned with the applications: TWI, CMM and FLOW. The major challenges arising in these areas of virtual metrology are collected in the following. We begin with a general discussion that applies to all applications considered.

2.1. General challenges when using VEs for uncertainty evaluation

Uncertainty evaluation in metrology is commonly performed using the principles of the GUM. According to these principles and regardless of the choice of uncertainty evaluation procedure, i.e. the proposed law of propagation of uncertainties (LPU) of the JCGM-100 document [42] or the proposed Monte Carlo (MC) propagation of state-of-knowledge distributions of the JCGM-101 document [41], an uncertainty evaluation relies on the definition of a measurement model and its input quantities. A measurement model defines the mapping of all input quantities, including the quantity corresponding to the observations, onto the measurand, i.e. the quantity of interest in the measurement. This is in stark contrast to the concept of a VE, which models the observation as a mapping of the input quantities and the measurand. See also Figure 1. With this clear conceptual difference, it is not straight-forward to include a VE into an uncertainty evaluation that complies with the principles of the GUM. While a complete Bayesian perspective following the discussion in the GUM-6 document [44] can be applied to a statistical model for the

Figure 1: Taken from [80] (CC BY 4.0). Comparison of virtual experiment and GUM measurement model: (a) generic virtual experiment that produces simulated observations given known values of measurand and input quantities. (b) Generic GUM measurement model which relates the measurand with observations and input quantities.

observations, cf. Section 3.4, also alternative approaches involving LPU and MC are performed in practice. These uncertainty evaluation methods are desirable, since they are comparably simpler than a Bayesian uncertainty evaluation and well-accepted in the community. However, one challenge that is considered in this guide is the validity and compliance of these approaches with the GUM document suite.

Another general challenge that is related to uncertainty evaluation is the effect of double-counting uncertainties. This should be avoided but the incorporation of a VE into the uncertainty evaluation might obscure this effect. This guide will discuss this effect on a simple linear example in Section 4.2.

Further general challenges for uncertainty evaluation are the identification and the cost-efficient quantification of all significant uncertainty sources. By incorporating new effects and quantities into the design of a VE, novel uncertainty sources can be analysed and a validation with real measurement data might reveal an uncertainty source that was previously not accounted for. A VE can also be used to quantify known uncertainty sources and assign values to known input quantities and their assumed uncertainties. To this end, statistical techniques like experimental design [8] can be used to build efficient and optimal plans to identify significant input parameters of a model and their impact based on an assumed uncertainty. To further increase the efficiency of these tasks, response surface design [1] and surrogate modelling [81, 73, 11] can be employed. These techniques might also be used to build a VE in the first place. Even though these topics are relevant for applications in virtual metrology and subject to current research, the corresponding discussions are out-of-scope for this GPG. For some of these research questions, e.g. regarding surrogate modelling and validation, we refer to the accompanying documents.

2.2. Embedded VEs – the TWI

The TWI requires a hybrid operation of the real measurement device and its virtual counterpart - its VE - to obtain the measurand, i.e., the form of a surface under test. This procedure is sometimes referred to as an embedded VE [54]. For more

details on the actual operation and the creation of a reference measurement system for the form measurement of aspheres and freeform surfaces see [19].

After adjusting the model to the real experiment with well-known reference surfaces, a subsequent measurement involves the acquisition of measurements from the current surface under test (SUT) in the laboratory and a numerical optimization of a virtual measurand, such that the VE produces (virtual) measurements that closely resemble the real measurements. In a first step, the virtual measurand is parametrized by Zernike polynomials and the coefficients are obtained during the optimization. Afterwards, a transformation is performed that i) translates the parametric polynomials to nonparametric pixel values corresponding to 3D coordinates, ii) adds higher frequency residuals to the form and iii) performs a fit of the resulting point-cloud into an initially assumed design. The resulting 3D point-cloud of this procedure represents the desired absolute form of the SUT and is the final measurand that is reported.

The VE of the TWI is numerically complex, since millions of rays are aimed and traced through an optical system for every creation of virtual measurements. Solving the involved inverse problems, i.e., estimating two parametric wavefront manipulators for adjusting the model to the real experiment, estimating the form of the SUT for the measurement and performing the transformation to obtain the final measurand, requires multiple calls of the VE.

Previous procedures to evaluate uncertainty involved in the measurements of the TWI usually rely on sensitivity analysis [20, 21] and the analytical computation of the Jacobian required [22]. Monte Carlo procedures involving surrogate models have been considered [4, 64]. Also, in [67], experimental design is used to identify the main influencing parameters during model adjustment and measurement.

Uncertainty evaluation methods that involve GUM-compliant Monte Carlo computations or the Bayesian paradigm for the VE that includes all significant uncertainty sources are required. Concluding, the main challenge of uncertainty evaluation methods for the TWI is the complexity of the measurement setup, the computations involved and the nature of the embedded VE.

2.3. VEs to enhance the evaluation of measurement uncertainty – the CMM

In this section we will give a brief and thereby necessarily incomplete introduction to VEs for CMMs, often also called VCMMs (virtual CMMs), highlighting some key ideas. A fuller treatment of VCMMs can be found, e.g., in [16]. Also part 4 of ISO 15530 [34] should be mentioned in this context. This section will also give a bit more information with respect to the required prior information on the parameter values before a VCMM can be used, and also the concept of Maximum Permissible Errors (MPEs) is shortly mentioned.

A VCMM is a virtual model of a Coordinate Measurement Machine (CMM). In other words, a VCMM models the impact of a set of uncertainty sources on the measured coordinates. Given the high variety of measurements a CMM can perform, the concept of task-related uncertainty assessment has been introduced. A VCMM can be used to calculate a task-specific measurement uncertainty.

The VCMM model typically contains various categories of uncertainty sources, each modelled by one or more parameters. One can distinguish between uncertainty sources related to the CMM itself (kinematic errors, probing errors, effect

of environmental conditions on the CMM, etc.), uncertainty sources related to the measured object (roughness, form deviation, temperature), as well as uncertainty sources related to the CMM operator (i.e. mounting effects).

Before a VCMM can be used, values and uncertainties for all these parameters are needed. Some parameter values and associated uncertainties can be taken from literature, e.g. the thermal expansion coefficient of the material of the CMM and/or of the artefact being measured. Kinematic errors can often be experimentally determined, either by measuring calibrated reference standards like a ball plate, or by using measurement standards, i.e., auxiliary instrumentation like an interferometer for a more direct measurement of the kinematic errors. Uncertainties related to the probing system can be evaluated by measuring a calibrated reference sphere. The repeatability of the machine can be evaluated by using repeated measurements, and the component due to mounting can be evaluated similarly.

Although CMM acceptance tests according to the ISO 10360 series [35, 38] can give some information on particular components of the involved parameters, these tests generally do not allow to determine the values of the VCMM parameters. These tests are used to assess the CMM performance for a highly specified task against the specifications provided by CMM manufacturers, typically provided in terms of MPEs.

Once a detailed mathematical model for a CMM has been built and all parameters have been determined, it can be used to evaluate task specific uncertainties for a great variety of measurement tasks.

Specific challenges relating to the operation of a VCMM and the calculation of measurement uncertainties that will be considered in this GPG are as follows:

- Various strategies are possible for using a VCMM to evaluate a task specific measurement uncertainty. Which one is the preferred option, and how sensitive are the results to the selected strategy?
- What should be done when the mean of the calculated probability distribution for the measurand using a VCMM is significantly different from the estimate based on the measured data alone?
- How does the typical formalism used in VCMMs comply with the GUM and statistical uncertainty evaluation in general?

2.4. Traceable VEs – the flow-meter calibration

In flow metrology, VEs can be used to simulate how the flow measurement is influenced by disturbed flow conditions. For this, the flow field is simulated with computational fluid dynamics (CFD) in a first step. In a second step, the measurement principle of the considered flow meter is applied to the calculated flow field. This virtually determined flow rate measurement can then be compared with the actual flow rate, providing an estimate of the fluid-mechanical calibration factor that needs to be applied for the considered disturbed flow condition. Of course, fluid-dynamical calibration factors can also be determined by measurements. In this case, the readings of the considered flow meter under different disturbed conditions are compared with a reference flow rate measurement. However, these measurements are costly and time-consuming as they have to be done for each

specific geometry separately. In contrast, VEs allow to consider a lot of different configurations, covering a wide range of possible velocity distributions and secondary flow motions. Furthermore, the influence of uncertainties in the input parameters on the resulting prediction and uncertainty of the flow rate can be investigated systematically.

Under the assumption that the VE fully reflects the real experimental set-up and takes into account all contributions of uncertainty, its predictions can be used to correct the flow rates measured under these conditions. Only by taking the uncertainty of the VE as well as the uncertainty of all influencing factors into account, one can ensure that the predictions are trustworthy. For this, the uncertainty of the VE needs to be determined. In the case of the virtual flow meter, this uncertainty is mainly caused by error of the CFD model used to compute the flow field, mostly due to turbulence modeling. In addition, as CFD simulations are computationally expensive, it might be necessary to use a surrogate model for the prediction of the flow field leading to additional errors in the prediction, which need to be taken into account.

More details regarding the virtual flow meter and the developed uncertainty evaluation method will be given in Section 6. Further details regarding the use and improvements of surrogate models will be discussed in [75].

3. General description of uncertainty evaluation methods

In Section 3.1 we introduce some terminology and notation, and define rigorously the term VE and interpret its structure in the context of virtual metrology. In Section 3.2 we consider various uncertainty evaluation methods that comply with the concept of LPU and in 3.3 we investigate MC-based uncertainty evaluation approaches. Finally in Section 3.4, we also discuss fully Bayesian methods and how VEs can be used in this framework for uncertainty evaluation.

3.1. Terminology and notation

The term virtual experiment (VE) is often rather loosely defined in many areas of science. While a quick numerical computation or the call of a computer code can be seen as performing an experiment on a (virtual) machine, i.e. a VE, this GPG considers a more formal definition. This definition is important in the context of virtual metrology and this GPG, since the aim is to establish a valid concept for uncertainty evaluation that can also be compared with well-established guidelines and frameworks for uncertainty evaluation in metrology.

Following the wording in the overview paper [51], a VE is a statistical model that is able to generate virtual observations. This concept of a VE is closely related to several publications in the field of virtual metrology, but may be different from other areas of science. For example, in [80], a VE is stated to be a numerical model of an experiment or a measurement process. It produces virtual data whose properties reflect those of the data observed in the corresponding real experiment. A formal mathematical description of a VE using the notation of a statistical model with attention to the challenges in measurement processes is given in [33]. Illuminating the connection between a VE and the required digital representation of

the measurement instrument, in [40, 48] the term virtual instrument is used for such a scenario. In this context, one of the main goals of the VE is to perform an uncertainty evaluation in conjunction with real measurement data, which will also be of primary interest in this work. In other publications where specific measurement devices and processes are modelled, similar terms describing their virtual representation are used, like virtual coordinate measuring machine (VCMM) in [31, 48], virtual flow meter in [68, 77], or virtual tilted-wave interferometer in [67]. In several publications, the concept that we call VE in this GPG is only defined in the context of DTs, mainly with the aim to distinguish the DT from general computing models and simulations [24].

In this GPG and also following [51], VEs are defined as mathematical/numerical models simulating, in a virtual environment, how the measurement data x , observed in a real experiment, are generated. To this end, the VE combines a deterministic mapping of certain input values with statistical elements that reflect the variability observed in a real experiment. Formally we may write similar to [33], a VE as a statistical model

$$x = G(y, z, \epsilon), \quad \epsilon \sim F. \quad (1)$$

Hereby, y denotes a specific value for the measurand Y , which is the quantity of interest in a measurement and for which ultimately an uncertainty evaluation has to be performed. For example in a CMM, Y denotes, e.g., the a priori unknown radius of a sphere that corresponds to the measurements x of the quantity X representing a spherical surface. The values z of the usually also multivariate parameter Z represent a variety of different elements, e.g., parameters representing physical quantities, characteristics of the measurement instrument, variances of error sources, hyperparameters, etc. In a real measurement, the actual parameter Z is unknown but fixed under repeated measurements. In contrast, ϵ , which is a realization of a random variable E with distribution F , is a statistical parameter that varies in repeated measurements. All statistical randomness in the observed quantity X is modelled by the variable E , and any additional variability or uncertainty is due to the uncertain but fixed parameters modelled by Z . These random influences introduced by E may classically be additive measurement noise, but can also constitute real physical quantities whose nature generates different values under repetition, not just under reproduction. All these quantities enter the mapping G , which reflects the real measurement process on a computer, and may influence the resulting virtual measurements x at any stage of the computation. Hereby, the mapping G might represent complex physical processes, such as scatterometric principles in terms of the solution of partial differential equations or it might model the effect of temperature deviations onto a measurement sensor. While this general structure of a VE in (1) offers a much more flexible modelling approach, it also challenges the applicability of well-known approaches for uncertainty evaluation, such as the uncertainty evaluation framework of the GUM using LPU or MC sampling.

The crucial difference to common uncertainty evaluation frameworks in metrology is that a VE takes values for the measurand as an input, whereas a measurement model [42], here also denoted by the term data analysis (DA), defines the (somewhat) inverse operation of the VE. In particular, the measurand quantity Y is the

output of the DA, given values for the measured (observed) quantity X and the model parameter Z . Since a measurement model is a mapping between quantities, one usually expresses the functional relationship by

$$Y = f(X, Z), \quad (2)$$

where f is sometimes called the 'measurement function', 'evaluation function', or 'inverse model'. The latter is, however, misleading, since a measurement model in metrology might not be invertible. Moreover, given a VE as in (1), the choice of a measurement model is ambiguous, which has already been discussed for simple regression models in metrology [12], where the choice of the Euclidean norm for the optimization might not be sufficient for a corresponding measurement model. This is also discussed in [71] for the CMM, where the impact of the choice of the measurement model is analysed. In some cases, there might be no actual dependence on Z when applying the evaluation function to the quantity X , e.g., when fitting a sphere to measured coordinates. In other cases, there can be a dependence on Z , e.g., in scatterometry the wavelength of the light is needed to calculate the critical dimension of the sample from the measured light intensity [47]. Moreover, it is possible that the evaluation function depends on additional parameters that are not used in the VE, but required for the DA, e.g., the degree of a polynomial that is fitted during the evaluation of the measurand [54].

Several approaches for uncertainty evaluation in the presence of a VE, a DA, and real measurement data have been proposed in literature. Notably [80, 33, 55, 32] present approaches that are also in accordance to the GUM standards in metrology [41]. In the following, we will recall in Section 3.2 several uncertainty evaluation procedures using linear approaches, such as LPU and in Section 3.3 also non-linear procedures that utilize MC.

3.2. Uncertainty evaluation by linearization

In this section, two methods for uncertainty evaluation are discussed, which are based on the concept on linearization to simplify the computations. The LPU method applied to the DA, i.e. the measurement function (2), which is also the suggested uncertainty evaluation method in the GUM, and the LPU method applied to the VE, which extends the ideas presented in the GUM to the concept of VEs.

3.2.1. LPU applied to the DA / the measurement function

The law of the propagation of uncertainty (LPU) based methods rely on the calculation of linear sensitivity coefficients and subsequent propagation of covariances as explained in the GUM, i.e. the JCGM 100 document [42] for univariate models and in JCGM 102 [43] for multivariate models. The required sensitivity coefficients, i.e., the partial derivatives of the DA function (2), can be calculated in a numerical or in an analytical way, and it can be done at different stages of the data analysis. In addition to the assignment of sensitivity coefficients, also all input quantities X and Z of the DA function needs to be assigned and require a value and an uncertainty. Then, the formula for the covariance of the measurand

Y based on the general LPU formula reads

$$U_Y = J_f U J_f^T, \quad (3)$$

where J_f denotes the Jacobian matrix, i.e. the sensitivity coefficients arranged in a matrix, of the DA function f with respect to all input quantities and U denotes the joint covariance matrix of X and Z . Usually in the GUM, this matrix is block-diagonal, since the observed quantity X is assumed independent to the input quantity Z . The uncertainty of each element of the (possibly multivariate) measurand is given by the square root of the diagonal elements of the covariance matrix U_Y and the off-diagonal elements of U_Y correspond to covariances of individual components of Y .

Requirements:

- Partial derivatives of the evaluation model function f with respect to the quantity X , i.e., $\frac{\partial f}{\partial X}$ and each element of the parameter $Z = (Z_1, \dots, Z_n)$, i.e., $\frac{\partial f}{\partial Z_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$.
- Evaluation of the partial derivatives at some estimate \hat{x} for X and \hat{Z} for Z yields the Jacobian matrix J_f .
- Covariance matrix of input quantities

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} U_X & U_{X,Z} \\ U_{Z,X} & U_Z \end{bmatrix}$$

with $U_X = u_X^2$ for the case of univariate observations, U_Z denoting the covariance matrix for the parameter vector Z , and $U_{X,Z}$ being the cross-covariance between the measurement data X and the parameter vector Z ,

$$U_{X,Z} = \text{cov}(X, Z) = \text{cov}(Z, X)^T = U_{Z,X}^T.$$

Constraints:

- The resulting uncertainty for the measurand is an approximation only if the evaluation function f is non-linear within the relevant domain defined by the input estimate and uncertainties. To account for non-linearities, higher order derivatives may be employed.
- No prior knowledge for the measurand Y can be employed.

Challenges

- Computations of the partial derivatives can be challenging, numerically and analytically.
- Correlations or covariances between sources of uncertainties or measurement data are not always available.

An approximation of the matrix valued approach above is obtained by ignoring correlations between the input quantities. For a detailed discussion and different levels of complexity, cf. JCGM 100 [42, clause 5].

The approach ‘LPU applied to the DA’ does not involve the VE explicitly. However, in several places a VE can be used also in this uncertainty evaluation approach. For instance, the measurement function f itself or the result of the uncertainty evaluation can be validated by means of an analysis involving the VE. Also the involved input quantities X and Z can be treated using a VE, e.g. by identifying the values or corresponding uncertainties of these quantities. This is also acknowledged in the GUM [42] itself, since the information about an uncertainty source can be obtained in many ways, for instance using simulations.

In the next section it will be shown how the DA can be directly related to the VE.

3.2.2. LPU applied to VE

This approach to uncertainty evaluation employs the VE directly by defining the measurement function / the DA (2) using the VE. A regression-like formulation can be of the following form:

$$Y = f(X, Z) = \operatorname{argmin}_{Y'} \|X - g_0(Y', Z)\|_2^2, \quad (4)$$

where $X = g_0(Y, Z) = G(Y, Z, \epsilon \equiv 0)$ denotes the VE without the addition of random measurement noise¹, i.e., the subscript zero is used to indicate that a deterministic ‘forward model’ is used. This formulation is, e.g., employed in the form reconstruction process of the TWI [19] or in the process of fitting certain parameters of a sphere to CMM measured data [6, 80, 48].

The estimate resulting from (4) is a (possibly local) optimum of the least-squares functional. In this report, we focus on two approaches to obtain the uncertainty corresponding to this estimate: the linear weighted-least-squares approach following [52] and the approach based on the implicit function theorem following [43, clause 6.3]. In [6] and [52], an overview of regression approaches involving the real measurements x and a ‘fitting model’ g_0 are presented.

Linear weighted-least-squares: The covariance obtained by the linear weighted-least-squares approach is given by

$$U_Y = \left(J_Y^T U_X^{-1} J_Y \right)^{-1}, \quad (5)$$

where J_Y denotes the partial derivative of the forward model function g_0 with respect to Y at the estimated values for Y and Z . These estimated values may be obtained using (4). The matrix U_X is the covariance corresponding to the measured quantity X . It is important to note that no uncertainty information about the additional parameter Z is considered in this approach, since specific values have been taken as estimates. Extensions to include the uncertainty in Z involve the concept of extended weighted-least-squares [61], weighted-total-least-squares [52] or the following approach based on implicit functions.

¹Using capital letters for the VE is an abuse of notation but the concept of a measurement model / measurement function, requires quantities as an input, whereas a VE takes values / vectors or random values / random vectors as input.

Implicit function theorem: This approach is, e.g., applied for scatterometry [26] and for details consider [43, clause 6.3]. There, the formula for the covariance of the measurand is given by

$$U_Y = J_Y^{-1} J_{X,Z} U J_{X,Z}^T J_Y^{-T}. \quad (6)$$

Here, U_Y is again the covariance matrix of the measurand Y , J_Y is the Jacobian of $-g_0(Y,Z)$ with respect to Y and J_Z the Jacobian of $-g_0(Y,Z)$ with respect to Z . It is to note that the minus sign is a result of the application of the implicit function theorem. However, this sign will cancel out in the actual formula (6). The matrix $J_{X,Z}$ is a block-diagonal matrix containing the identity matrix of the same dimension as X and J_Z . If J_Y is rectangular, having more rows than columns but of full-rank, J_Y^{-1} denotes the Moore-Penrose left-inverse matrix $(J_Y^T J_Y)^{-1} J_Y^T$ and J_Y^{-T} denotes its transpose. U denotes the covariance matrix of the vector (X,Z) , i.e., of both measurement data having covariance matrix U_X and additional parameters Z having covariance matrix U_Z . A schematic overview of this method is shown in Figure 2. It is also possible to split up the computation in separate terms addressing the uncertainty in X ('type A uncertainty') and the uncertainty in Z ('type B uncertainty') when X and Z are uncorrelated. This procedure is used in, e.g., [26].

Figure 2: Schematic overview of the LPU using the VE uncertainty evaluation method. Taken from [51] (CC BY 4.0).

The following requirements, constraints and challenges have been identified for the application of either the linear weighted-least-squares regression or the approach based on implicit functions for real measurement data and VEs.

Requirements:

- The VE must be linear or can reasonably be approximated by a linear function, e.g., using a Taylor expansion at some estimate.
- The covariance U_X of the measured quantity X and the covariance U_Z of the input quantity Z are required. Additionally, the (cross-) covariance between X and Z can be included, if available, to form the full covariance

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} U_X & \text{cov}(X, Z) \\ \text{cov}(Z, X) & U_Z \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

Constraints:

- The method is based on a linearization of the least-squares functional and is an approximation in the case of non-linear VEs. To overcome this issue, higher order derivatives of the VE are required.
- No prior knowledge for the measurand Y can be employed.

Challenges

- High dimensionality: the matrix inversions required can be numerically challenging.
- Singularity: the matrix U_X or U might be (almost) singular due to the correlation structure. Also the matrix J_Y might be singular due to highly correlated model parameters or because two (or more) parameters describe the same effect.

The VE here is included in the model construction process, i.e. the DA is build using the VE. Therefore, this kind of uncertainty evaluation can be seen as compliant with the uncertainty evaluation framework of the GUM. However, it should be assessed whether the resulting measurement model function (4) actually models the measurement. Model uncertainty might arise from employing the VE in this sense, which needs to be assessed by, e.g., model validation techniques.

3.3. Monte–Carlo based uncertainty evaluation

In this Section we discuss uncertainty evaluation methods that rely on the Bayesian interpretation of probability and the propagation of distributions (PoD). The JCGM 101 [41] considers an easily applicable Monte Carlo sampling approach, which assigns state-of-knowledge distributions to the input quantities of the measurement functions (2) and subsequently propagates these distributions through the measurement function. We will recall this method in Section 3.3.1 and highlight some aspects, where a VE can be employed. Subsequently, we discuss in Section 3.3.2 a scheme for uncertainty evaluation using PoD that incorporates the VE directly. And finally, in Section 3.3.3 we discuss a PoD approach for uncertainty evaluation that obtains the same result as a GUM MC sampling approach, when certain assumptions are met.

3.3.1. PoD as presented also in GUM Supplement 1 and Suppelement 2

In the JCGM 101 [41], JCGM 102 [43] and related GUM documents, a set of independent, real observations and a measurement model function (2) are required to perform an uncertainty evaluation. For multivariate observations, the $m \geq 1$ repeated observations $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_m$ are taken for the $n \geq 1$ observed quantities X_1, \dots, X_n , i.e., every observation $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_i^1, \dots, x_i^n)$ is a vector that may represent different measurement locations, wavelengths, or parameter settings, depending on the application considered. The corresponding quantity for which the observations are assumed to be realizations of is denoted by X , and it is required to have more observations than dimensions $m > n$. The measurement model function (2),

which relates the input quantities X and additional parameters Z to the measurand Y , is denoted by f . However, especially in higher dimensions, the choice of the measurement model can be challenging, and even though the measurement model function (2) can be taken as the partial inverse of the virtual experiment (1), this is by no means the only option and ambiguous. In fact, the measurement model function can deviate from the choice in (2) and we will analyse this in the example of a coordinate measuring machine in Section 5.2.

For the multivariate JCGM 102 Monte Carlo approach, we assume there is some measurement model function (2) given and a probability density function (PDF) $\pi(z)$ for the quantity Z , which may be the result of expert elicitation or the explicit guidance in JCGM 101 [41]. For the measured quantity X , JCGM 102 assigns in clause 5.3.2 a multivariate scaled and shifted t-distribution with $\nu = m - n$ degrees of freedom. To ensure the uncertainty, i.e. the covariance, is well-defined, it is required to have $\nu > 2$. The shift by the experimental mean vector and the scaling through the scaled experimental covariance are based on the observations $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_m$. In particular, one assigns

$$\pi(x) = t_\nu(\bar{x} = (\bar{x}^1, \dots, \bar{x}^n), S/m), \quad \bar{x}^j = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m x_i^j, \quad S = \frac{1}{\nu} \sum_{i=1}^m (\mathbf{x}_i - \bar{x})(\mathbf{x}_i - \bar{x})^T, \quad (8)$$

where t_ν denotes the PDF of the corresponding multivariate t distribution. Sampling from the multivariate scaled and shifted t-distribution can be accomplished by sampling from a multivariate standard normal distribution and scaling and shifting the samples accordingly. In particular, for a random vector θ following a multivariate normal distribution with mean μ , covariance Σ_N , and η following a multivariate scaled and shifted t-distribution as in (8), the following equality² holds:

$$\eta = S^{1/2} \frac{\Sigma_N^{-1/2}(\theta - \mu)}{\sqrt{\varphi}} \frac{\sqrt{\nu}}{\sqrt{m}} + \bar{x}, \quad \eta \sim t_\nu(\bar{x}, S/m), \theta \sim N(\mu, \Sigma), \varphi \sim \chi^2(\nu). \quad (9)$$

Here, φ is a random variable that follows a χ^2 -distribution with ν degrees of freedom. The matrix square roots of the symmetric positive definite covariance matrices S and Σ_N can be obtained, for example, by the Cholesky decomposition. This means that drawing samples from a t-distribution can be realized by combining samples from a normal distribution with samples from a χ^2 -distribution. For more details, cf. [43] (clause 5.3.2.4) and [49].

At this point it is interesting to note that the requirement $m > n$, i.e., assuming more observations than dimensions in the observed quantity, can be omitted when assuming a known covariance of the observations. In this case, a multivariate normal distribution with estimate \bar{x} can be assigned instead of a multivariate t-distribution [41, clause 6.4.8]. This includes the case of $m = 1$, which is commonly considered for the coordinate measuring machine. However, in this work, we focus on the case of an unknown covariance in the observations.

Based on this PDF assignment for the quantity X and the availability of a PDF for the quantity Z , the following Monte Carlo sampling Algorithm 1 may be applied to represent the state-of-knowledge distribution for the measurand.

²this equality holds in distribution, which means, the random vector on the left-hand side and the random vector on the right-hand side of the equality symbol follow the same distribution

Algorithm 1 JCGM-102 Monte Carlo algorithm

Input: Measurement model function $f(X, Z)$, real observations $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_m$, state-of-knowledge PDF $\pi(z)$, number of samples N .

Output: Samples from state-of-knowledge PDF of measurand $\pi(Y)$

- 1: Compute state-of-knowledge PDF $\pi(x)$ for the quantity X as in (8)
- 2: for $i = 1, \dots, N$ do
- 3: $z'_i \leftarrow$ Draw sample from PDF $\pi(z)$
- 4: $x'_i \leftarrow$ Draw sample from PDF $\pi(x)$
- 5: $y'_i \leftarrow$ Evaluate measurement model $f(x'_i, z'_i)$
- 6: end for
- 7: Summarize samples y'_1, \dots, y'_N to obtain estimate and corresponding uncertainty in terms of the mean vector and the covariance matrix

$$\hat{y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y'_i, \quad U_Y = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (y'_i - \hat{y})(y'_i - \hat{y})^T. \quad (10)$$

- 8: The standard uncertainty of every element of Y is given by the square root of the diagonal elements of U_Y .
-

3.3.2. PoD using the VE

This method requires that a simple data evaluation function (SDE) of the form

$$Y = f_0(X) = f(X, Z = \hat{z}_0). \quad (11)$$

is available. The function f_0 that can be used to compute a value of the measurand based on the data alone, using a fixed estimate \hat{z}_0 of the input quantity Z . This SDE allows to obtain an estimate of the measurand, but does not incorporate the effects of all influence on the measurand. Instead, the effect of all influence quantities is propagated to the measured data X by means of the VE, evaluating what we will call here ‘total data uncertainty’, and as a last step the SDE is applied. This idea has also been applied in Section 3.2.1 when using the linear-weighted least-squares approach. In practice, this method is most often used in combination with a MC method, leading to the following procedure.

1. Fix an estimate y_0 of Y for the artefact parameters. This estimate will be used in the VE later on.
2. For a large number of repetitions, sample $z^{(j)}$ from $\pi(z)$ and $e^{(j)}$ from F , i.e., the random elements of the VE in (1).
3. Calculate $x^{(j)}$ using the VE evaluated in $(y_0, z^{(j)}, e^{(j)})$ and compute $y^{(j)}$ using the SDE.
4. From the $y^{(j)}$ a value of the uncertainty from y_0 can be computed, e.g., the standard deviation of the sample set $y^{(1)}, y^{(2)}, \dots$

In this approach it is assumed that all uncertainties are known. In the first step it requires an estimate of Y to be used in the VE. This estimate can be either based on the observed measurement data x or on a nominal value for Y . Depending on

the sensitivity of the calculated uncertainty on the used estimate y_0 , this choice does or does not significantly affect the calculated uncertainty, see also the study in [48].

We now discuss three options for the selection of the estimate of the measurand. The first choice $y_{\text{VE-SDE-A}}$ results from simply taking the mean $\overline{y^{(j)}}$ of the samples $y^{(j)}$, which may seem natural at first sight, as it resembles the procedure of PoD of [41]. However, in this case this value may not depend at all on the measured data if for y_0 simply a nominal value has been used. This approach will therefore not be further pursued. The second alternative $y_{\text{VE-SDE-B}}$ is to use as an estimate the value y_0 obtained by applying the SDE to the data, and using the samples only to calculate the uncertainty, as what is sometimes done for VCMMs [31]. This can be interpreted as shifting the distribution of the samples $y^{(j)}$ by the difference between the mean of the samples $\overline{y^{(j)}}$ and y_0 . A third option is to use the VE to assess the bias in the SDE by taking into account the known ground true value $y_{\text{sim,true}}$ of the measurand of the simulated measurand. The spread in the samples is then a measure of the uncertainty in the bias. The samples can then be used to correct the potentially biased estimate $y_{\text{VE-SDE-B}} = y_0$ to get an unbiased estimate $y_{\text{VE-SDE-C}}$ of the measurand. As the bias is estimated to be $\overline{y^{(j)}} - y_{\text{sim,true}}$ this results in $y_{\text{VE-SDE-C}} = y_{\text{VE-SDE-B}} - (\overline{y^{(j)}} - y_{\text{sim,true}})$. If the VE is evaluated at the value y_0 corresponding to $y_{\text{sim,true}} = y_{\text{VE-SDE-B}}$ this results in $y_{\text{VE-SDE-C}} = 2y_{\text{VE-SDE-B}} - \overline{y^{(j)}}$. Note that this involves a reflection of the distribution w.r.t. $y = y_{\text{VE-SDE-B}}$, which is relevant if the distribution of the samples $y^{(j)}$ is asymmetric.

In practice, most often $y_{\text{VE-SDE-B}}$ is used as estimate \hat{y} of the measurand, as this value is based on the measurement data alone and requires no information on the uncertainties of Z and E . However, if \hat{y} lies outside the coverage interval that can be calculated using the simulated $y^{(j)}$, this estimate is significantly biased from a statistical perspective. In such cases, if $y_{\text{VE-SDE-B}}$ is to be retained, it may be wise to either report the bias separately or to increase the uncertainty of \hat{y} for the observed bias of the SDE. In section 5.2 we show an example for this case.

In the case that calibrated measurement standards are available, the bias for the particular measurand can also be experimentally corrected for by substitution measurements, instead of using this model-based approach.

The GUM suite of documents does not explicitly describe any variant of the procedure ‘VE-SDE’ as described in this section as an option, therefore one may doubt the strict GUM-compliance of this method, notwithstanding that this method intends to take into account all uncertainty sources and propagate them through a function f_0 using the propagation of distributions idea. Also note that in this approach ideal (or measured) data are perturbed with measurement errors, whereas in the GUM approach measurement data X are corrected for errors. The resulting distribution for Y produced by the ‘VE-SDE-A’ and ‘VE-SDE-B’ approaches will therefore generally be mirrored compared to the GUM solution based on PoD applied to a measurement function that explicitly inverts the VE. Only in the case of a sufficiently well-behaved model and symmetric distributions of the uncertainty sources, the numerical difference in the result will be very small or zero.

Another issue that makes strict GUM-compliance of the VE-SDE approach questionable is the following. If the uncertainty is calculated for the idealized points based on the measurement plan which is the ideal shape of the artefact in ideal po-

sition, it is not clear if the calculated uncertainty is also valid for the real shape in real position. If the uncertainty is not calculated for the result computed from the measurement data, but for some proxy believed to lie close to it (i.e., incorrectly assuming that if $y_1 \approx y_2$ then $u(y_1) \approx u(y_2)$), then the uncertainty may be significantly higher in reality. E.g., in a CMM the probing angle may not lie between two angles $-\alpha$ and $+\alpha$ as simulated, but rather between $\beta - \alpha$ and $\beta + \alpha$ for some angles α and β due to misalignment. So the here presented VE-SDE approach may underestimate uncertainties if solely idealized input data is used, and strict GUM-compliance of this approach can therefore be questioned.

In industrial practice, a more realistic uncertainty value can actually be calculated by performing VE-based uncertainty calculations under a range of non-ideal simulated circumstances, i.e., by using suitable values of α and β .

Finally note that in industrial practice, part of the uncertainty contributions may be dealt with by means of a simulation model, whereas additional ones have to be considered separately.

3.3.3. MC-VE: equivalent to MC GUM in certain scenarios

In this section, we present a method for uncertainty evaluation that can be applied to VEs (1), which ensures that the resulting distribution for the measurand has, under certain assumptions, the same properties as the distribution generated by GUM Supplement 1 using the measurement function (2) instead. The presented Monte Carlo sampling approach will use the VE as a black-box and simply utilize the virtual observations that are generated by the VE. A particular transformation will subsequently be employed to transform the distribution of the virtual measurements to the distribution of some available real measurements. Finally, the distribution of the measurand will be obtained via repeated evaluation of an approximate measurement function, obtained from the VE.

The profound benefit of this approach is one does not require knowledge of the VE model itself, and thus the VE can be used in a ‘black-box approach’ where one only uses the generated measurement data. This includes the fact that neither the complex physical models behind the VE nor the propagation of the probabilistic elements need to be explicitly accounted for by the user.

This approach has been developed for different scenarios. A procedure that is exact for linear VEs has been published in [80]. An appropriate algorithm for a wider class of nonlinear VEs is provided in [33]. For the multivariate case with unknown (co-)variance, the algorithm is stated in [55]. An additional inclusion of prior knowledge regarding the precision of the measurement instrument is considered in [32].

In the following, we present a variant of the MC-VE algorithm that is published in [55]. The paper introduces a robust numerical method for uncertainty evaluation that integrates VEs with MC sampling. This approach enables the propagation of uncertainties in complex and non-linear measurement function (2), enhancing compliance with the GUM framework for uncertainty evaluation while offering greater flexibility compared to traditional linearization-based methods.

There are two main issues when using a virtual experiment, as in (1), for uncertainty evaluation for the measurand. Firstly, every evaluation of the virtual experiment requires a value y for the measurand as input. Since the true value for

the measurand is generally unknown, virtual observations generated by the virtual experiment will most likely differ from real observations and estimates for the measurand using these virtual observation may admit a bias as discussed in the previous section. For the algorithm developed later in this section, we will show that any simulated value y_0 for the measurand can be taken, without affecting the resulting estimate and its associated uncertainty. Secondly, repeated realizations from the virtual experiment are drawn from a multivariate probability distribution F . On the other hand, the JCGM 102 approach considers a multivariate t-distribution and considers correlations, which are informed by real observations with unknown variances. Assuming the virtual experiment is a black-box and the distribution of the random deviations, represented by ϵ in (1), cannot be altered, the random variable representing the virtual observations needs to be corrected to comply with the JCGM 102 MC sampling approach. For this, the mean of the virtual experiment is required, i.e, for some value of the measurand y and some value of the parameter vector z , one either has direct access to the forward model $\mu := g_0(y, z)$ or alternatively, one may estimate the mean from additional evaluations of the virtual experiment and a Monte Carlo estimate using many samples, here denoted by N_{ve}

$$\mu = g_0(y, z) = \mathbb{E}_{\epsilon \sim F} [G(y, z, \epsilon)] \approx \frac{1}{N_{ve}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{ve}} (G(y, z, \epsilon_j)) \quad (12)$$

Additionally, for the following Monte Carlo algorithm 2 to generate the same PDF as JCGM-102 and algorithm 1, we require knowledge about the gradient of the forward model to transform between the observations and the measurand. This gradient is formed by the partial derivatives of the forward model g_0 with respect to the measurand, $J^{ve}(y_0, z) := \frac{\partial g_0}{\partial y}(y, z)|_{y=y_0}$, evaluated at some value for the measurand y_0 and any z . Since this gradient might be inaccessible in a black-box virtual experiment, it may be obtained by assuming that derivatives of the VE are available, in the sense the VE also outputs a partial derivative for every evaluation of (1). Then one may estimate the derivatives of the forward model for some N_{ve} large enough using

$$J^{ve}(y_0, z) = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} g_0(y, z)|_{y=y_0} = \mathbb{E}_{\epsilon \sim F} \left[\frac{\partial G}{\partial y}(y, z, \epsilon)|_{y=y_0} \right] \approx \frac{1}{N_{ve}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{ve}} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y} G(y, z, \epsilon_j)|_{y=y_0} \right), \quad (13)$$

Both cases are realistic in the sense that a black-box virtual experiment might directly return the gradient of the forward model, since it may have been an essential part of the computations required, e.g., when g_0 involves some optimization functional. Also, samples of a disturbed gradient might be present when an automatic differentiation tool is used after evaluation of the virtual experiment or when a gradient approximation is performed using finite difference methods.

With these ingredients, we present the following Monte Carlo sampling algorithm 2, based only on the evaluation of a virtual experiment, that yields the same state-of-knowledge PDF for the measurand, as the JCGM 102 MC sampling approach.

The algorithm 2 effectively produces samples from the same distribution as the Monte Carlo sampling approach of JCGM-102 in algorithm 1 using the measurement model function (2). This is because equation (16) corrects the assumed

variances $\sigma_1^2, \dots, \sigma_n^2$ to the t-distribution that accounts for the assumption of an a priori unknown variance of the data distribution, and also implicitly applies an approximated measurement model function (2). This means that algorithm 2 prescribes the employed measurement model. However, for algorithm 2 we only require evaluations of the virtual experiment and its gradient. In particular, no explicit knowledge about the VE is required and realizations of the VE can be noisy.

The algorithm 2 developed in this Section yields samples of the same PDF as JCGM 102 and algorithm 1 under the assumption that the VE and the measurement model function follow a specific semi-linear structure. In particular, assuming that the measurement model function (2) is affine linear in the observed quantity X and possibly non-linear in the additional quantity Z , i.e. of the form

$$Y = \Delta_1(Z)X + \Delta_2(Z) \quad (18)$$

for some functions $\Delta_1(Z)$ and $\Delta_2(Z)$, the sampling algorithm 2 yields asymptotically the same estimates for the mean and covariance matrix as the algorithm 1. For more general classes of virtual experiments and measurement models, the approach presented can be seen as a linearization procedure that considers, for every realization of the quantity Z , a local linearization in the measurand Y . The effect of taking a non-linear measurement model function and a linearized virtual experiment is analyzed for the coordinate measuring machine in Section 5.2. A suitable alternative approach that may account for these kinds of models is a Bayesian approach, employing a statistical model based on the virtual experiment (1).

3.4. Bayesian methods

In this section uncertainty evaluation methods based on the Bayesian paradigm will be discussed [25]. The Bayesian paradigm relies on probability calculus and moreover on the concept of degree of belief. This means, an uncertainty about some parameter is expressed in terms of a distribution or probability density function (PDF) and a given state-of-knowledge about some quantity, expressed by said PDF. This interpretation of the term uncertainty and its use in the context of metrology and VEs has already been discussed in the previous sections of this GPG. However, the essential part of Bayesian methods is that a degree of believe is updated in the presence of new data using Bayes' rule.

To formulate this approach, a statistical model for the observed data x and prior knowledge about the involved quantities Z and the measurand Y is required. This prior knowledge is subsequently combined with the measurement data x , giving rise to a posterior distribution. This latter distribution can be used to calculate and present the measurement uncertainty of, e.g., the measurand Y . Obtaining estimates for the uncertainty from the posterior distribution, e.g., in terms of moments or coverage probabilities, is in general challenging and statistical and numerical techniques, such as Markov Chain Monte Carlo or variational inference, are required. However, in contrast to the methods previously discussed, the Bayesian approach allows to incorporate prior knowledge regarding the measurand Y . This can efficiently reduce the measurement uncertainty, by including informative expert knowledge or historical measurements.

It is common in the presence of VEs to incorporate the forward model in the statistical model. For example, a statistical model assuming homoscedastic Gaussian observations with given parameter Z , measurand Y , and variance σ^2 can be written as

$$x | Y, Z, \sigma^2 \sim N(g_0(Y, Z), \sigma^2 I) \quad (19)$$

This is a special case of the VE defined in (1) and utilizes the forward model from 4. Prior knowledge about the measurand Y , the parameter Z , and the variance σ^2 can be employed to obtain the posterior distribution of all these quantities, given the data x . The PDF of the measurand can be obtained by marginalization. However, the Bayesian approach is not limited to the models above. Some variants that are usually considered are

- Non-Gaussian data distributions
- Heteroscedastic models using diagonal or full covariances
- Hierarchical models with random hyperparameters

The Bayesian approach is, e.g., employed in problems involving scatterometry [30]. Here, also the modelling of surrogate models plays an important role, since the computation of the posterior distribution can be numerically demanding. The following general requirements, constraints and challenges have been identified

Requirements:

- Statistical model that can reasonably be assigned for the observations.
- Prior knowledge, in terms of distributions, for the parameters of the statistical model.
- Numerical scheme to obtain estimates from the posterior distribution.

Constraints:

- The first two moments of the posterior PDF must exist to obtain an estimate for the value and for the uncertainty of the measurand to be finite.

Challenges:

- Informative prior knowledge for the measurand may not be available but can be extracted from historical data, the VE, and expert elicitation.
- Non-informative prior knowledge is an important concept in the direction of objective Bayesian inference. However, constructing non-informative prior distributions is not always straightforward. Additionally, ensuring the existence of the posterior PDF and, in particular, that an estimate and an uncertainty can be extracted from it, is usually a challenging task.
- Analytical formulas for the mean or variance of the posterior PDF are rarely available and numerical schemes to extract properties from the posterior usually require extensive evaluation of the posterior PDF or the forward model. This can be computationally demanding.

- Numerical procedures usually imply statistical sampling techniques, such as Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC), for which a convergence analysis is required and possibly a case-by-case proposal mechanism. This challenges the general applicability of Bayesian methods.
- Numerical stability issues may arise when evaluating the posterior PDF in regions of low probability, which can happen based on the design of the forward model and the prior.

3.4.1. Bayes' Theorem and the posterior distribution

Bayes' theorem provides a principled way to update our beliefs about unknown parameters in light of observed data. In the course of the GPG, the unknown parameters are the quantities Y, Z . Given a statistical model and prior knowledge, Bayes' theorem yields the posterior distribution of the parameters.

For illustration of the general principle, consider the statistical model of the form (19) above where $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the observed data, Y and Z are parameters / quantities of interest, and σ^2 is the variance. We denote the joint prior distribution over parameters as $\pi(Y, Z, \sigma^2)$.

Then, the posterior distribution is given by Bayes' theorem:

$$\pi(Y, Z, \sigma^2 | x) = \frac{p(x | Y, Z, \sigma^2) \pi(Y, Z, \sigma^2)}{p(x)},$$

where the marginal likelihood or evidence $p(x)$ is a constant for given measurements x :

$$p(x) = \int p(x | Y, Z, \sigma^2) \pi(Y, Z, \sigma^2) dY dZ d\sigma^2.$$

The likelihood function $p(x | Y, Z, \sigma^2)$ depends on the statistical model (19) and reads for this specific choice

$$p(x | Y, Z, \sigma^2) \propto \sigma^{-n/2} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \|x - g_0(Y, Z)\|_2^2\right). \quad (20)$$

Let us consider two different cases for knowledge about the variance of the measurement data.

3.4.2. Case 1: Known variance

When σ^2 is known, the posterior simplifies to:

$$\pi(Y, Z | x, \sigma^2) \propto p(x | Y, Z, \sigma^2) \pi(Y, Z).$$

The likelihood function is:

$$p(x | Y, Z, \sigma^2) = \frac{1}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{n/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \|x - g_0(Y, Z)\|_2^2\right).$$

Thus, the posterior becomes:

$$\pi(Y, Z | x, \sigma^2) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \|x - g(Y, Z)\|_2^2\right) \pi(Y, Z).$$

Inference can then proceed by either sampling from or optimizing this posterior, depending on the context.

At this point it is important to note that the Bayesian approach treats the quantities Y and Z both as inference parameters and updates their degree of believe based on the measurements available. This is in contrast to the GUM uncertainty framework, for which only the measurand Y is treated as an inference variable. Therefore, if one is only interested in the posterior distribution of the measurand, a marginalization over the variable Z has to be performed

$$\pi(Y | x, \sigma^2) \propto \int \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}\|x - g(Y, Z)\|^2\right) \pi(Y, Z) dZ. \quad (21)$$

This can usually only be done numerically.

Case 2: Unknown variance with Prior Knowledge Now suppose σ^2 is unknown, which is a typical scenario in metrology. In this case, prior knowledge can be assigned to the parameter σ and for computational reasons, it is often beneficial to consider an inverse-gamma prior, since it follows as a conjugate prior to the model (19):

$$\sigma^2 \sim \text{Inv-Gamma}(\alpha, \beta),$$

and that it is independent of Y and Z , i.e.,

$$\pi(Y, Z, \sigma^2) = \pi(Y, Z) \cdot \pi(\sigma^2),$$

with:

$$\pi(\sigma^2) = \frac{\beta^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)} (\sigma^2)^{-\alpha-1} \exp\left(-\frac{\beta}{\sigma^2}\right).$$

For some guidance on the choice of the parameters α and β depending on the knowledge about the precision of the measurement instrument, consider the work in [79, 58, 53]. Then the joint posterior is:

$$\pi(Y, Z, \sigma^2 | x) \propto p(x | Y, Z, \sigma^2) \pi(Y, Z) \pi(\sigma^2).$$

Plugging in the likelihood and prior:

$$\pi(Y, Z, \sigma^2 | x) \propto (\sigma^2)^{-n/2} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}\|x - g(Y, Z)\|^2\right) \pi(Y, Z) (\sigma^2)^{-\alpha-1} \exp\left(-\frac{\beta}{\sigma^2}\right),$$

which simplifies to:

$$\pi(Y, Z, \sigma^2 | x) \propto (\sigma^2)^{-(\alpha + \frac{n}{2})-1} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{\sigma^2} \left(\frac{1}{2}\|x - g(Y, Z)\|^2 + \beta\right)\right) \pi(Y, Z).$$

This corresponds, up to a multiplicative constant, to an inverse-gamma distribution in σ^2 , conditional on Y and Z . Therefore, the conditional posterior is:

$$\sigma^2 | x, Y, Z \sim \text{Inv-Gamma}\left(\alpha + \frac{n}{2}, \beta + \frac{1}{2}\|x - g(Y, Z)\|^2\right),$$

and the marginal posterior for (Y, Z) is obtained by integrating out σ^2 , typically intractable analytically but feasible via sampling techniques (e.g., Gibbs sampling). Generalizing these concepts to the more general case of VEs (1) is rather straightforward but depends strongly on the actual structure of the VE $G(y, z, \epsilon)$ and its properties. Also the form of the random contributions $\epsilon \sim F$ are important and the choice taken here as an additive influence $F = N(0, \sigma^2 I)$ is not always suitable.

3.4.3. Computational methods to assess the posterior distribution

In many Bayesian models, the (marginal) posterior distribution $\pi(Y | x)$ cannot be derived analytically due to non-conjugate priors or complex likelihoods. To approximate quantities such as the posterior mean $\mathbb{E}[Y | x]$ as an estimate for the value of the measurand and the posterior standard deviation $\text{SD}(Y | x)$ as an estimate for the standard uncertainty of the measurand, several numerical methods have been developed. Below we summarize four widely used approaches.

Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) MCMC methods generate correlated samples from the posterior distribution by constructing a Markov chain whose stationary distribution is $\pi(Y | x)$. A common example that comprises a large class of sampling approaches is the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm. Given samples $\{Y^{(s)}\}_{s=1}^S$, the posterior mean and variance are estimated as:

$$\hat{\mu} = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{s=1}^S Y^{(s)}, \quad \hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{1}{S-1} \sum_{s=1}^S (Y^{(s)} - \hat{\mu})^2.$$

MCMC is widely applicable but can suffer from slow convergence in high-dimensional or strongly correlated parameter spaces [27, 60].

Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) HMC improves sampling efficiency by introducing auxiliary momentum variables and simulating Hamiltonian dynamics. It uses gradients of the log-posterior to propose distant moves with high acceptance probability. This results in lower autocorrelation and faster convergence than traditional MCMC [57, 9]. Modern implementations (e.g., in Stan) automate tuning of step size and trajectory length.

Variational Inference (VI) VI approximates the posterior with a tractable family of distributions $q_\lambda(Y)$ by minimizing the Kullback-Leibler divergence $\text{KL}(q_\lambda(Y) || \pi(Y | x))$. This results in a fast, optimization-based approach to posterior approximation. While computationally efficient, VI can underestimate uncertainty due to the restrictive form of q_λ [10, 45].

Laplace Approximation Laplace's method approximates the posterior with a Gaussian centred at the mode \hat{Y}_{MAP} , i.e. the point with the highest probability - the maximum a posteriori (MAP) - in the posterior PDF, using the curvature of the log-posterior:

$$\pi(Y | x) \approx \mathcal{N}(\hat{Y}_{\text{MAP}}, [-\nabla^2 \log \pi(Y | x)|_{\hat{\theta}_{\text{MAP}}}]^{-1}).$$

It is efficient and works well when the posterior is unimodal and approximately Gaussian near the mode [50, 78].

Each of these methods trades off computational cost, flexibility, and accuracy. In practice, the choice depends on the model structure and desired level of approximation.

Especially for metrological applications, certain MC sampling approaches can be derived that simplify the usually complex and time-consuming approaches discussed above. An approach based on inverse transform sampling, including explicit

guidance on the choice of hyperparameters is presented in [79]. An approach based on rejection sampling that generates iid samples from the posterior distribution can be found here [56]. Another approximate approach to compute the posterior distribution is given below for the TWI 4.3.

4. Example 1: Uncertainty evaluation for tilted-wave interferometry

At the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), the national metrology institute of Germany, a reference measurement system for the form of aspheres (and freeform surfaces) based on a tilted-wave interferometer (TWI) [3, 23, 2] is under development [19]. The TWI belongs to the non-null test measurement methods. The measurement principle of the TWI combines interferometric measurements with ray tracing, perturbation methods and mathematical evaluation procedures. A key aspect of the measurement principle of the TWI is that a VE is required to obtain the measurand desired [19], i.e., the form of the SUT. This VE, closely resembles the measurement process of the TWI. This includes the optical system (lenses, apertures, camera, etc.), ray-tracing and ray-aiming algorithms, and a model for the form of the SUT. Additionally, statistical fluctuations of the measurement can be incorporated into the VE by simulating random effects on physical input quantities. In the VE of the TWI, the form of the SUT is parameterized by an a priori known design form and a difference form. During the measurement process, the measurements of the real-world TWI are used to adjust the parameters of the difference form in the VE by solving an inverse problem. This embedded structure of the TWI and its VE to obtain the measurand challenges the application of classical approaches to measurement uncertainty, e.g., the techniques considered in the GUM (JCGM 100) or its supplements (JCGM 101/102).

In this section of this GPG we will first consider the VE of the TWI in Section 4.1 and subsequently discuss two approaches for uncertainty evaluation that involves the VE of the TWI. On the one hand, a linearized approach using the LPU of Section 3.2 is derived in Section 4.2 and subsequently a more involved statistical approach using the Bayesian paradigm as discussed in Section 3.4 is developed in Section 4.3.

4.1. The VE of the TWI

The basic measurement setup of the TWI is shown in Figure 3. The light of a laser is split by a beamsplitter into the reference arm and the measurement arm of the interferometer. The measurement arm is equipped with a 2D microlens array, where each microlens acts as a single point light source. With this setup, each microlens generates a differently tilted wavefront behind the collimator that illuminates the SUT. A beam stop in the Fourier plane of the imaging optics avoids sub-sampling effects by blocking the light that would produce non-resolvable fringe densities at the camera. Depending on the local slope of the specimen, the light from a different microlens generates resolvable sub-interferograms, referred to as patches, at the camera. These patches contain information about the form of the SUT. To avoid interference between the light of neighbouring microlenses, a

Figure 3: Sketch of the basic setup of the TWI (adjusted from [19], CC BY 4.0).

special mask behind the microlens array blocks the light from every second row and column of the 2D microlens array, so that four measurements with four different mask positions are needed to acquire the images from all possible microlenses. For each of the four measurements, a five-step phase shifting algorithm [29] together with the Goldstein unwrapper [28] are used to calculate the optical path length differences (OPDs), i.e., the differences between the optical path lengths (OPLs) of the reference arm and the measurement arm, from the interferograms. Since the positioning of the SUT within the measurement setup, especially along the optical axis, is important, the setup is equipped with an additional distance-measuring interferometer, which measures the relative axial position of the SUT during the alignment procedures. In order to reconstruct the form of the SUT from these OPDs, a VE of the setup and the SUT is used to model the OPDs for the assumed surface form. By solving an inverse problem, the parameters of the assumed surface form are adjusted in an iterative process, until the measured and modeled OPDs match to each other. Since the VE is part of the reconstruction process, the model used has to be adjusted to the real experiment in order to reflect the behaviour of the real setup. For this purpose, highly accurate, well-known reference surfaces are measured at many positions of the measurement setup. The measurement results are compared to realizations of the VE and several model parameters, i.e. so-called wavefront manipulators that are parametrized using Zernike polynomials, are adjusted by solving another high-dimensional inverse problem. Further details of this procedure can be found e.g. [19] and this process will not be described in more detail in this GPG.

The measurement concepts of the TWI are replicated in a virtual environment using the optical simulation toolbox SimOptDevice [63]. Mathematically, this defines a numerical function $g(\theta, Z)$ that models OPDs that closely resemble the OPDs from the real-world TWI. We will refer to $g(\theta, Z)$ as the forward model of the TWI, since we want to distinguish between the deterministic forward model of the VE and the VE itself. In the forward model, the parameter θ represents an a priori unknown description for the form of the SUT together with its position and orientation within the setup. The form is parametrized by the design description (for an asphere, e.g., the aspherical formula of [59, 17]), Zernike polynomials [76], which are commonly employed to describe variations in optics, and a non-parametric model correction term that is able to reflect higher-frequency

Table 1: Quantities and their assumed uncertainties used in the application tilted-wave interferometer within this GPG. In the column ‘Quantity’, the general symbols for VEs are used, whereas the column ‘Pseudonym’ introduces more context specific variable names.

Quantity	Pseudonym	Value	Unit	Remark
X		-	m	Optical Path Differences (OPDs) extracted from the TWI measurement data. Capital X denotes the quantity and x the actual observation.
Y	θ	-	m	Multivariate measurand: surface form and further inference parameters, like offset and position parameters.
Z_1	Δz	0	m	Deviation of SUT position in z-direction
Z_2	$\Delta \alpha$	0	rad	Deviation of SUT orientation in α -direction
Z_3	$\Delta \beta$	0	rad	Deviation of SUT orientation in β -direction
Z_4	$\Delta \gamma$	0	rad	Deviation of SUT orientation in γ -direction
Z_5	Z_{wav}	\hat{Z}_{wav}	-	Model correction parameters of wavefront manipulators, i.e. coefficients of Zernike polynomials, estimate \hat{Z}_{wav} obtained by model correction procedure
u_x	σ	1×10^{-8}	m	Uncertainty of OPDs, i.e. assumed noise
u_{z1}		1×10^{-6}	m	Uncertainty in Z_1
u_{z2}		3×10^{-4}	rad	Uncertainty in Z_2
u_{z3}		3×10^{-4}	rad	Uncertainty in Z_3
u_{z4}		3×10^{-4}	rad	Uncertainty in Z_4
u_{z5}		Γ_{wav}	-	covariance matrix of Z_5 , i.e. of coefficients of Zernike polynomials

terms of the surface form. Moreover, θ comprises a set of latent variables that are required for an efficient solution of the following inverse problem. In particular, each patch of the acquired interferograms has an offset value corresponding to a shift of the OPDs of that patch, since the OPDs of each patch can only be calculated from the measurement data up to an unknown offset value. The multivariate parameter Z collects additional parameters of the experiment that are required to replicate the TWI measurements in a virtual environment, i.e., the configurations of the lens-systems, the position of the collimator and CCD, the wavelength of the laser employed, the parameters of the model adjustment, to name just a few. For details on the elements of θ and Z , cf. e.g. [18, 19] and [54]. A list of parameters considered in this GPG is given in Table 1.

At this point it is to note that the list of parameters and uncertainty sources in Table 1 is not exhaustive and many more parameters are known to influence the uncertainty of the TWI, e.g., the form of the reference surfaces used for the correction of the model, ambient conditions, the wavelength of the laser (if not

measured with high accuracy) and other parameters, see e.g. [18, 67]. Also, a realistic determination of the standard deviation of the influencing factors is challenging and subject to future research. Here, only rough orders of magnitude are chosen in order to demonstrate the methods developed in the project.

The observations of the TWI, i.e. the high-dimensional OPDs x that are acquired by the TWI are statistically modelled as realizations of the following homoscedastic model

$$X | \theta, Z, \sigma^2 \sim N(g(\theta, Z), \sigma^2 I), \quad \sigma^2 > 0 \text{ known.} \quad (22)$$

For this section, this statistical model is considered to be the VE of the TWI, where the forward model $g(\theta, Z)$ is simply the mean function of a normal distribution with known standard deviation σ for the measurements. In future research, more statistical deviations than pure random measurement noise will be considered. Also, more influencing parameters are to be considered to accurately model the TWI measurement and heteroscedasticity or more involved distribution assumptions might be considered.

In the following sections, we will derive two approaches to perform uncertainty evaluation using the VE (22).

4.2. A linearized approach to uncertainty evaluation for the TWI

The developments in this section implement a simplified, i.e., linearized variant of the tilted-wave interferometer (TWI) and provide uncertainty evaluation for this simplified model. The purpose of this section is therefore not the accurate representation of the measurement principle of the TWI, but a practical consideration of different uncertainty evaluation procedures when dealing with VEs. Important concepts, such as heads-up model correction, higher-frequency terms and post-processing of the difference form obtained (residual projection and fit-in-design (i.e. correction of the surface positioning)), are not included in this study. Hence, the results are not representative of the actual TWI and may differ significantly from uncertainties obtained in real experiments. Unless otherwise noted, the VE of the TWI in this section refers to this simplified and linearized version.

4.2.1. The VE of the (Simplified) TWI

The simplified VE of the TWI in this section is modeled as:

$$X = g(\theta, Z) + \varepsilon = A_\theta \theta + A_Z Z + \varepsilon$$

Here:

- A_θ and A_Z are matrices representing different parameter influences (analytically or numerically obtained),
- θ is the measurand vector, in this case only a limited set of polynomial coefficients and positioning parameters,
- Z is a multivariate parameter vector with additional parameter influences, c.f. Table 1,
- ε is homoscedastic Gaussian noise with known standard deviation σ .

Due to the linearity of the model, one particular choice of the measurement model can be derived from the VE by inversion as:

$$\theta = A_{\theta}^{\dagger}(X - A_z Z)$$

where A_{θ}^{\dagger} is the pseudoinverse of the matrix A_{θ} . It is important to note that this choice of the measurement model is done in accordance to the choice of the VE. Alternative measurement models can be derived from expert knowledge and by other means. It is nevertheless common (but not always correct) to interpret a measurement model as a partial inverse of an observation model. For a more in-depth discussion of this topic in the context of uncertainty evaluation, measurement models according to the GUM and statistical models for the observations, we refer to [13, 14, 12, 53] and the references therein.

Figure 4: Example OPDs generated by the linearized TWI on the camera. Root-mean-square values per 2D image are shown in the header of each image. The images correspond to a single measurement with the four different illumination settings. These generated observations are dominated by position effects and would be corrected in a real measurement scenario prior to the reconstruction of the topography (measurement).

An example observation is given in Figure 4, where it can already be seen that the misalignment of the SUT is a dominant influence. Since the actual TWI includes sophisticated alignment procedures and a non-linear post-processing step that corrects for possible misalignment after reconstruction of the surface form, this effect has little influence on the resulting uncertainty for the actual TWI measurement. In this scenario, this alignment and post-processing steps are not included in the linear expansion and therefore, the error in the reconstruction and the magnitude of the uncertainty obtained will be larger.

For the generation of these measurements, a Zernike polynomial with 228 coefficients $\theta^* = (\theta_1^*, \dots, \theta_p^*)$ has been chosen, together with a random collection of Z values sampled from an assumed Gaussian distribution with mean and standard deviation according to Table 1. The aim of the following estimation and uncertainty evaluation methods is to estimate the value of θ^* and its corresponding uncertainty, assuming the available measurement in Figure 4.

4.2.2. Results for uncertainty evaluation applied to the benchmark scenario for the simplified TWI

In the following, we apply the uncertainty evaluation methods that involve the simplified VE defined above and evaluate the results. We restrict the investigation to four methods:

- LPU using the DA from Section 3.2.1
- LPU using the VE from Section 3.2.2
- PoD applied to the DA from Section 3.3.1
- PoD applied to the VE followed by the DA from Section 3.3.2

In all cases, we evaluate the covariance of the measurand θ . Due to the linearity of the VE and measurement model, it is possible to obtain analytical formulas for the resulting uncertainty of the measurand. This approach outlines the behaviour of the individual methods and offers insights into the actual dependence on the uncertainty sources, models and the way the VE is included into the uncertainty evaluation procedure.

LPU using the DA: An estimate for the measurand θ is obtained using estimates for all input quantities and application of the measurement model. The corresponding uncertainty is obtained using derivatives of the measurement model, in particular one obtains for the covariance matrix of the measurand

$$U_\theta = \begin{bmatrix} A_\theta^\dagger & -A_\theta^\dagger A_Z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_X & 0 \\ 0 & U_Z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} (A_\theta^\dagger)^T \\ -(A_\theta^\dagger A_Z)^T \end{bmatrix}, \quad (23)$$

Where U_X denotes the covariance of the observed OPDs $U_X = \sigma^2 I$ and U_Z is the covariance matrix associated to the multivariate quantity Z , cf. Table 1. Since this uncertainty, i.e. covariance is obtained using LPU applied to the measurement model, it is actually the result of an uncertainty evaluation according to the GUM.

LPU using the VE: An estimate of this method is either generated by solving the (linear, weighted) least-squares problem

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} \sigma^{-2} \|x - A_\theta \theta - A_Z \hat{Z}\|_2^2$$

for some measurement x and estimate \hat{Z} of the quantity Z , or by solving the implicit function

$$h(x, \theta, Z) = \theta - A_\theta^\dagger x - A_\theta^\dagger A_Z Z = 0. \quad (24)$$

Estimating an uncertainty for the least-squares approach, as derived above, is performed using the following formula

$$U_\theta = (J_\theta^T U_X^{-1} J_\theta)^{-1} = \sigma^2 (A_\theta^T A_\theta)^{-1} = \sigma^2 A_\theta^\dagger (A_Y^\dagger)^T, \quad (25)$$

where J_θ is the respective partial derivative of the VE function g with respect to θ .

This approach ignores the variability in the quantity Z , since an estimate \hat{Z} is taken for Z . Therefore, this approach is not suitable when variability in the Z quantity is significant. On the other hand, using the implicit function, one can derive the uncertainty of the measurand by taking the corresponding derivatives J_θ and $J_{X,Z}$ of h and using

$$U_\theta = J_\theta^{-1} J_{X,Z} U J_{X,Z}^T J_\theta^{-T} = \begin{bmatrix} -A_\theta^\dagger & -A_\theta^\dagger A_Z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_X & 0 \\ 0 & U_Z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -A_\theta^\dagger \\ -A_\theta^\dagger A_Z \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

$$= \sigma^2 A_\theta^\dagger (A_\theta^\dagger)^T + A_\theta^\dagger A_Z U_Z A_Z^T (A_\theta^\dagger)^T. \quad (27)$$

This latter approach is, due to the linearity of the assumed VE, equivalent to the application of the LPU using the DA approach and correctly accounts for the variability in the quantity Z . This is to be expected, since the formulation of the implicit function assumes no fixed value for Z . This observation carries over to other uncertainty evaluation methods, which make use of intermediate estimates. To further illuminate this aspect, a third alternative that could be considered for the LPU using the VE approach is a joint regression for the θ and Z quantity. This requires solving the least-squares functional for both variables simultaneously and therefore puts additional requirements on A_Z to ensure solvability and the existence of the estimate

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \hat{Z} \end{bmatrix} = \arg \min_{\theta', Z'} \|x - \begin{bmatrix} A_\theta & A_Z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta' \\ Z' \end{bmatrix}\|_2^2 = \begin{bmatrix} A_\theta & A_Z \end{bmatrix}^\dagger x \quad (28)$$

as well as to ensure that this point is not a saddle-point of the functional. The uncertainty, i.e. covariance matrix, corresponding to the estimate of θ can be obtained by obtaining the joint covariance matrix of θ, Z and, due to the linearity and Gaussianity of the approach, rows and columns of this matrix corresponding to Z can be ignored. Since an analytical comparison would require a more closed-form solution, this approach is not applied in the following.

PoD applied to the DA: This approach performs a propagation of distribution, usually using Monte Carlo sampling, by applying the measurement model to realizations of the input variables Z and $x + J_Z^g \epsilon_Z + \epsilon = x + A_Z \epsilon_Z + \epsilon$, where ϵ is a Gaussian error realization with standard deviation σ , J_Z^g is the partial derivative of the VE model function g , and ϵ_Z is a realization of the error introduced by the Z quantity, i.e. a realization of $N(0, U_Z)$, assuming a multivariate Gaussian distribution with values according to Table 1. Due to the linearity of the VE, the resulting distribution can again be evaluated analytically. It holds,

$$(x + A_Z \epsilon_Z + \epsilon) \sim N(x, \sigma^2 I + A_Z U_Z A_Z^T) \quad (29)$$

and applying the measurement model yields

$$\theta \sim N\left(A_{\theta}^{\dagger}(x - A_Z \hat{Z}), \sigma^2 A_{\theta}^{\dagger} (A_{\theta}^{\dagger})^T + 2A_{\theta}^{\dagger} A_Z U_Z A_Z^T (A_{\theta}^{\dagger})^T\right). \quad (30)$$

The additional factor in the covariance that doubles the effect of the uncertainty source Z is due to the fact that the uncertainty of Z enters in the distortion of the measured value $x + A_Z \epsilon_Z + \epsilon$ and due to the measurement model $f(x + A_Z \epsilon_Z + \epsilon, Z)$, effectively double-counting uncertainties. Therefore, this method is not suitable for application to the TWI, where elements of Z may have a dominant impact on the resulting uncertainty. However, if there is a clear distinction between elements of Z affecting the VE and disjoint elements of Z affecting the measurement model, this method is applicable and does not double-count uncertainties. This is, for instance, the case for the CMM, where the measurement model usually does not depend on Z . Alternatively and to avoid the double-counting of the uncertainties, a fixed distortion of the measurements can be applied. This may come at the cost of a bias.

PoD applied to the VE followed by the DA: This approach performs a propagation of distribution, usually using Monte Carlo, of the VE as input to the first entry of the measurement model. In particular, the distribution of $\theta = f(g(\theta_0, Z), Z)$ is analyzed using a simulated quantity θ_0 that has values that are close to the true, but unknown, measurand value. For the linear VE with $Z \pi(Z)$, an arbitrary state-of-knowledge distribution for Z , and some value θ_0 of θ , it follows

$$f(g(\theta_0, Z), Z) = f(A_{\theta} \theta_0 + A_Z Z + \epsilon, Z) = A_{\theta}^{\dagger} (A_{\theta} \theta_0 + A_Z Z + \epsilon - A_Z Z) \quad (31)$$

$$= \theta_0 + A_{\theta}^{\dagger} \epsilon \sim N(\theta_0, \sigma^2 A_{\theta}^{\dagger} (A_{\theta}^{\dagger})^T). \quad (32)$$

Here, as in the approach LPU using the VE with the least-squares approach, the uncertainty of the Z quantity is neglected. Again, if the elements of Z accessing the VE are disjoint with the measurement model, this approach might yield adequate results. Similarly, as above, this effect can be negated when taking a deterministic value for the distortion $+A_Z Z$ and only considering the correction $-A_Z Z$ as random. However, this may again introduce a bias in the estimation. Also note that the estimate strongly depends on the chosen value θ_0 . When taking $\theta_0 = A_{\theta}^{\dagger}(\theta - A_Z Z)$ as the estimate from the measurement model using the estimate \hat{Z} , this again yields the same estimate for $\hat{\theta}$ as the previous approaches.

The application of the discussed approaches to a linearized version of the TWI can be found in Appendix Section A.

4.3. A Bayesian approach to uncertainty evaluation for the TWI

Following the work in [54], this section applies the Bayesian approach to the inverse problem of the TWI and to the task of uncertainty estimation. To tackle the computational complexity, an approximate Bayesian inference for the posterior PDF is developed that allows for efficient independent Monte Carlo sampling to compute the uncertainty corresponding to the unknown parameters. The developed approach is then applied to the TWI, by taking into account a number of key influencing factors, to demonstrate the performance of the methodology.

In contrast to the Section regarding Bayesian uncertainty evaluation 3.4, the goal here is to perform uncertainty quantification for the usually obtained estimate of the TWI measurement. This is a different approach than considering the full posterior distribution and deriving an estimate and uncertainty from the resulting PDF. However, since the estimate of the TWI is computed using well designed measurement principles and incorporates a lot of expert knowledge regarding the optimization, it is justifiable to derive a corresponding uncertainty for this specific estimate, rather than changing the estimate in accordance to the statistical model. For this, let us denote $\hat{\theta}_Z$ as the usual estimate of the TWI measurand when performing the measurement. We indicate the use of the estimate \hat{Z} , partially obtained by calibration and expert knowledge. To perform uncertainty evaluation using the Bayesian approach, consider the prior knowledge $\pi(\theta, Z) = \pi(\theta)\pi(Z)$, which assumes independence between the inference parameter θ and the additional parameter in the forward model Z . Note that, for $\pi(Z)$ we assume perfect prior knowledge for the parameters that correspond to the optical systems and we assume a prior PDF for the model correction parameters (i.e. Zernike coefficients of the wavefront manipulators), which has been derived [54]. Then, using the statistical model (22), the joint posterior PDF is given by

$$\pi(\theta, Z | y) = h(x) \exp\left(-\|x - g(\theta, Z)\|_2^2 / 2\sigma^2\right) \pi(\theta)\pi(Z), \quad (33)$$

where the constant $h(x)$, i.e., the evidence, normalizes the posterior PDF, such that it integrates to one. Throughout this work, it is assumed that this PDF exists. For more details and requirements on the function g to ensure existence, propriety and the existence of moments for the posterior, cf. eg. [25, 69]. Marginalization over the parameter Z yields the marginal posterior PDF for the parameter of interest θ . This PDF reflects the state of knowledge about this parameter after consideration of the data x . Now, the covariance of the estimate $\hat{\theta}_Z$ with respect to this marginal posterior is the quantity that describes the sought uncertainty under the available state of knowledge. This covariance matrix is given by

$$\begin{aligned} U &= \mathbb{E}_{\theta|x} \left[(\theta - \hat{\theta}_Z)(\theta - \hat{\theta}_Z)^T \right] \\ &= h(x) \int \int (\theta - \hat{\theta}_Z)(\theta - \hat{\theta}_Z)^T \exp\left(-\|x - g(\theta, Z)\|_2^2 / 2\sigma^2\right) d\pi(\theta)d\pi(Z), \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

which requires the computation of a multivariate integral over a non-linear function involving the forward model, which is in general not feasible and a suitable approximation is required. Therefore, a partial first order Taylor expansion of the forward model in the parameter θ is performed: $g(\theta, Z) \approx g(\hat{\theta}, Z) + J(\hat{\theta}, Z)(\theta - \hat{\theta})$, where $J(\hat{\theta}, Z)$ denotes the Jacobian matrix of the function g around some expansion point $\hat{\theta}$, which is here the estimate from the TWI measurement using the variable parameter Z instead of the assumed true estimate \hat{Z} . It is to note that $\hat{\theta}$ does not usually equal $\hat{\theta}_Z$.

The linearization allows analytical integration with respect to θ in the integral (34), assuming a constant (non-informative) prior for the measurand $\pi(\theta) \propto 1$ and a full-rank Jacobian matrix for every Z . Then, the covariance matrix desired can reasonably be approximated by

$$U \approx \int \sigma^2 \left(J(\hat{\theta}, Z)^T J(\hat{\theta}, Z) \right)^{-1} + (\hat{\theta} - \hat{\theta}_Z)(\hat{\theta} - \hat{\theta}_Z)^T d\pi(Z), \quad (35)$$

where the quality of the approximation depends on the quality of the Taylor approximation. The covariance matrix U can therefore be obtained by Monte Carlo sampling. A detailed derivation of the formula (35) is given in the Appendix of [54]. It should be noted that the choice of a non-informative prior for θ is for mathematical convenience and can be replaced by a vague prior with large variance without significantly affecting the resulting uncertainty.

To numerically stabilize the computations and reduce the complexity of the Jacobian matrix $J(\hat{\theta}, Z)$ that has to be assembled for every Z , a decomposition is performed. To accelerate the computations in (35), a singular value decomposition of the Jacobian is chosen to be $\tilde{U}\Lambda V^T = J(\hat{\theta}, Z)$, since the required matrix inversion simplifies to

$$(J(\hat{\theta}, Z)^T J(\hat{\theta}, Z))^{-1} = V\Lambda^{-2}V^T. \quad (36)$$

Hence, computations can be limited to the orthogonal matrix V and the singular values of the Jacobian, which are, by construction of the measurement procedure always greater than 0.

The uncertainty estimation procedure for the TWI derived above is outlined in Algorithm 3. Note again that this algorithm can be employed for similar applications, involving models as (22), just as well.

Algorithm 3 Approximate Bayesian uncertainty evaluation, adjusted from [54], CC BY 4.0

Input: Computation model $g(\theta, Z)$, prior $\pi(\theta, Z) \propto \pi(Z)$, number of samples N , OPDs from model correction measurements x_c , OPDs from actual measurement x .

Output: Approximate covariance for estimate $\hat{\theta}$ according to (35).

- 1: Perform a model correction procedure to estimate \hat{Z} given x_c ▶ Expensive but required only once
- 2: Perform a measurement to estimate $\hat{\theta}_Z$ given x ▶ Done in any case to obtain an estimate
- 3: for $i = 1, \dots, N$ do
- 4: $Z_i \leftarrow$ Draw from prior $\pi(Z)$
- 5: $\hat{\theta}_i \leftarrow$ Perform a measurement to obtain current estimate using a disturbed system using x and Z_i .
- 6: $J(\hat{\theta}_i, Z_i) \leftarrow$ Calculate Jacobian at current estimate $(\hat{\theta}_i, Z_i)$.
- 7: $U_i\Lambda_iV_i^T = J(\hat{\theta}_i, Z_i) \leftarrow$ Perform singular value decomposition.
- 8: Store matrix V_i and vectors $\hat{\theta}_i$ and Λ_i in memory.
- 9: end for
- 10: Compute approximate covariance matrix

$$U \approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma^2 V_i \Lambda_i^{-2} V_i^T + (\hat{\theta}_i - \hat{\theta}_Z)(\hat{\theta}_i - \hat{\theta}_Z)^T \quad (37)$$

The measurement data considered in this GPG is simulated by the software SimOpt-Device [63] based on real measurement results obtained from the actual TWI. The reason for this choice is that higher frequency deviations of the SUT have not been considered in the uncertainty evaluation scheme of [54] and are therefore removed

and replaced by Gaussian measurement noise with standard deviation $\sigma = 10$ nm on the OPDs.

The steep asphere considered here is made of glass, has a clear aperture of 28 mm, and was also analyzed in an interlaboratory comparison in [62, asphere 4]. Details about the mathematical description of the asphere, as well as of the model correction and measurement of this asphere using the TWI at PTB are given in [19, section 4.2]. Similar to the results presented in the reference, we evaluate the form of the asphere on a surface diameter of 24.7 mm. For the reconstruction parameter θ of the aspherical surface form, 217 offset parameter and 228 polynomial coefficients are considered. As described above, the inclusion of higher frequency terms in the uncertainty evaluation of θ has not been performed.

Figure 5: Result for the estimate and uncertainty evaluation of the asphere considered for the TWI use-case and the assumed input uncertainties (see Table 1. It is shown in a) the absolute form of the SUT, in b) the estimate of the difference from the design using the original reconstruction procedure, in c) the pixel-wise standard uncertainty from the parametric/polynomial fit obtained by the Bayesian approach (note that this uncertainty is an intermediate result that does not reflect the actual uncertainty of the TWI estimate), and in d) the result for the pixel-wise standard uncertainty, for the influencing parameters considered, after applying the post-processing step that is described in [19] and [54]. Source: [54], CC BY 4.0.

In Figure 5 a) we show the estimated absolute form of the surface of the asphere considered and in b) its deviation from the assumed aspherical design form, cf. [19, section 4.2]. The intermediate result of the Bayesian uncertainty evaluation procedure presented in Algorithm 3 is shown in c) of Figure 5. Hereby, the standard uncertainty shown is obtained by transforming the covariance matrix of the Zernike coefficients obtained by the algorithm to a pixel-wise representation using the linear transformation defined by the Zernike polynomials evaluated at roughly 50000 equidistant points in the circle shown. Subsequently, the square root of the diagonal entries of the resulting matrix is the pixel-wise standard deviation or standard uncertainty of the polynomial fit. Since the positioning and orientation of the SUT is not corrected at this stage, the resulting uncertainty is still large. Note that this result has no practical relevance, but is shown here to demonstrate the two-step approach to generate the final uncertainty estimation of the final measurand. Finally, in d) the standard uncertainty of the measurand, i.e., the aspherical surface, obtained after the post-processing step that is described in [19] and [54], which resolves the ambiguity between the inferred surface form

and deviations in the position and orientation of the SUT.

It can be seen in Figure 5 c) that the standard uncertainty of the Zernike fit with up to 450 nm and a rms value taken over all pixels of 320 nm is quite large. As mentioned above, this result is of no practical relevance, since the positioning $\Delta x, \Delta y$ and orientation $\Delta \alpha, \Delta \beta$ is corrected in the post-processing step. The final resulting standard uncertainty after correcting these parameters is shown in Figure 5 d). Here, the standard uncertainty is reduced to a maximum of 65 nm in the center region and a rms value of 31 nm. The spatial distribution of the final standard uncertainty for the absolute surface form in d) is explained by the remaining dominant uncertainty source of the positioning of the SUT along the optical axis Δz , which causes a spherical form deviation and has already been identified as a main source of uncertainty in previous publications, cf. e.g. [23, 67]. The results presented correspond to an input uncertainty with a standard deviation of 1 μm for Δz . This value can be reduced by proper alignment strategies and additional measurements and its determination and optimization is part of current research [23, 65, 66].

Note that for the asphere considered, the parameter $\Delta \gamma$ is considered without uncertainty, i.e. it is fixed to the value 0 rad due to the symmetry of the specimen. Note further that the uncertainty shown in Figure 5 d) is already the pixel-wise standard uncertainty of the absolute surface shown in a), since adding a fixed design as a constant to an uncertainty does not change the result.

5. Example 2: Uncertainty evaluation for coordinate metrology

This section presents an example for uncertainty evaluation involving a VE from coordinate metrology. More specifically, a coordinate measuring machine (CMM) is studied. In section 5.1 the VE for the CMM is introduced. In section 5.2 the results of the uncertainty calculations for various uncertainty evaluation methods from section 3 are presented. Next, we discuss some further alternative modelling and uncertainty evaluation options in section 5.3 and we shortly discuss the concept of GUM-compliance in section 5.4. This section ends with some recommendations and lessons learnt in section 5.5.

5.1. The VE of the CMM

In this section we will present a simplified VCMM, which will hopefully help the reader to better understand the concepts discussed in this section.

The measurement data consists of measured coordinates $\mathbf{X} = (X_{ij})_{1 \leq i \leq n_x, 1 \leq j \leq d_x}$ of n_x points which are d_x -dimensional. In this section we will consider a 2-dimensional problem, i.e., $d_x = 2$, and the measured artefact is approximately circular.

The measurand vector \mathbf{Y} has two main components, and some auxiliary components. The measurands of interest to the end-user are Y_1 , which corresponds to the circle radius associated with the artefact, and Y_2 , corresponding to the peak-to-valley roundness, see also ISO-12181 [36, 37]. These measurands can be evaluated using a least-squares circle fit or minimum-zone circle fit to the measurement data, whereby form deviations such as the roundness are preferably evaluated using minimum-zone fitting. Some further parameters are needed to completely

specify the artefact shape and the measurement procedure, which will also be part of the parameter vector \mathbf{Y} . In this case, the parameters Y_3 and Y_4 correspond to the (true) centre of the circular artefact, the parameters Y_5 and Y_6 are additional parameters modelling the form deviations (a sine function added to a constant circle radius) and the parameters Y_7 to Y_{n_x+6} correspond to the angles at which measurement points are taken. The parameters Y_3 to Y_{n_x+6} are generally not of direct interest to the end-user, but they could nevertheless be estimated from the measurement data and they are required to be able to evaluate the VE function $\mathbf{X} = g(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{Z})$.

The parameter vector \mathbf{Z} corresponds to the instrument imperfections, i.e., the uncertainty sources related to the CMM itself. In our case this includes a linear scale error Z_1 of the CMM's x -axis, a linear scale error Z_2 of the CMM's y -axis and a squareness error Z_3 modelling the deviation from $\pi/2$ of the angle between the CMM's x - and y -axes. The standard deviation of the measurement noise $u_x = \sigma$ is treated as a known parameter in this case study. The parameters and their values are shown in table 2 and are taken from [71].

Note that in this GPG, a VE is formulated as $\mathbf{X} = g(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{Z})$. A VCMM as used in practice has often a slightly different structure and can be of the form $\mathbf{X} = \tilde{g}(\mathbf{X}_{\text{in}}, \mathbf{Z})$, whereby \mathbf{X}_{in} are usually either nominal coordinate data or real measurement data, though also simulated data corresponding to an imperfect artefact can be used. There is actually a close link between \mathbf{Y} and \mathbf{X}_{in} . If \mathbf{X}_{in} contains nominal data or simulated, noise-free imperfect data, then there is a one-to-one correspondence with \mathbf{Y} . If \mathbf{X}_{in} contains measurement data, the vector \mathbf{Y} can be estimated from the measured data and the other way round \mathbf{Y} can be used to simulate measurement data. Differences between using g and \tilde{g} correspond at most to higher order effects and can in most cases be neglected³. However, the choice for \mathbf{X}_{in} can matter, as discussed in section 5.3.1.

We now describe the equations specifying the simplified VE of a CMM. We will use variable names which are more common in this context. They are listed as 'pseudonyms' in table 2. Only for the Cartesian (x, y) -coordinates we use the letters (p, q) to avoid confusion with the symbols for the measurement data (X) and the measurands (Y), and similarly for the associated measurands P_i and Q_i in capital letters. For each of the n_x data points, a measurement angle Φ_i ($1 \leq i \leq n_x$) is calculated according to

$$\Phi_i = 2\pi i/n_x. \quad (38)$$

Starting with the circle radius R_0 , the lobe amplitude A , an offset angle Φ_{lob} and the number of lobes n_{lob} , the distance from the centre point R_i of point i is computed according to

$$R_i = R_0 + A \sin(n_{\text{lob}}\Phi_i + \Phi_{\text{lob}}). \quad (39)$$

Given the true centre coordinates $(X_{\text{cen}}, Y_{\text{cen}})$, the true point coordinates $(P_{\text{true},i}, Q_{\text{true},i})$

³The magnitude of an uncertainty source, e.g., a kinematic error, usually changes slowly over the CMM volume, which is typically in the order of 1 m. So differences in the input data in the order of 1 μm due to using slightly different inputs are usually not important.

Table 2: Parameters used in the application from coordinate metrology. In the column ‘Quantity’, the general symbols for VEs are used, whereas the column ‘Pseudonym’ introduces more context specific variable names. For the data vector \mathbf{X} no values are given as it would require too much space, for the measurand vector \mathbf{Y} the provided value corresponds to the mean ground true values used in the simulations, for the parameter vector \mathbf{Z} the provided value corresponds to the available estimate, equal to the mean of the probability distribution for that variable. The corresponding standard uncertainties are provided as u_{z1} , etc., and have been taken from [71].

Quantity	Pseudonym	Value	Unit	Remark
$X_{i,1} (1 \leq i \leq n_x)$	P_i	-	m	First coordinate of point i (“ x -coordinate”, in this section called p -coordinate)
$X_{i,2} (1 \leq i \leq n_x)$	Q_i	-	m	Second coordinate of point i (“ y -coordinate”, in this section called q -coordinate)
Y_1	R_0	100.036	mm	Radius of the best-fit circle to the artefact
Y_2	$2A$	0.05	mm	Artefact roundness, equal to twice the lobe amplitude
Y_3	P_{cen}	0.001	mm	p -coordinate of the circle centre of the artefact
Y_4	Q_{cen}	0.002	mm	q -coordinate of the circle centre of the artefact
Y_5	Φ_{lob}	0	rad	Start angle of the sine function associated with the artefact
Y_6	n_{lob}	3	-	Number of lobes in the artefact
Y_7 to Y_{n_x+6}	Φ_1 to Φ_{n_x}	$i\pi/n_x$	rad	Angles on the artefact circumference at which measurements are taken
Z_1	S_p	0	mm/mm	Estimate of the linear scale error of the p -axis (“ x -axis”)
Z_2	S_q	0	mm/mm	Estimate of the linear scale error of the q -axis (“ y -axis”)
Z_3	S_{pq}	0	rad	Estimate of the squareness error between the p - and q -axis
n_x	-	1000	-	Number of measurement points
u_x	σ	5.00×10^{-4}	mm	Uncertainty in the X_{ij} , measurement noise
u_{z1}	u_{sx}	1.15×10^{-4}	mm	Uncertainty in Z_1
u_{z2}	u_{sy}	1.15×10^{-4}	mm	Uncertainty in Z_2
u_{z3}	u_{sxy}	1.15×10^{-4}	rad	Uncertainty in Z_3

Figure 6: Schematic explanation of the impact of the squareness error α (in the main text denoted as S_{pq}) of the CMM axes on the measured coordinates. The true and CMM-axis are chosen to be identical, while the CMM squareness error α affects the direction of the q -axis in the CMM. The coordinates of a point in a true Cartesian coordinate system are (p_0, q_0) . The CMM measures (p'_0, q'_0) with respect to its own coordinate frame (assuming that readings are correctly performed orthogonal to each axis). The relationship of the measured coordinates to a truly Cartesian coordinate system follow from some geometrical and algebraic computations.

of the artefact are given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} P_{\text{true},i} \\ Q_{\text{true},i} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} P_{\text{cen}} \\ Q_{\text{cen}} \end{pmatrix} + R_i \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\Phi_i) \\ \sin(\Phi_i) \end{pmatrix} \quad (40)$$

The measurement of these points is affected by the measurement errors of the CMM. The systematic linear scale errors S_p and S_q of the p - and q -axis result in deformed coordinates according to $(1 + S_p) P_{\text{true},i}$ and $(1 + S_q) Q_{\text{true},i}$ ($1 \leq i \leq n$). Additionally, the true angle between the p - and q -axis is not perfectly 90 degrees, leading to a squareness error quantified by the angle S_{pq} - expressed in radians - as sketched in Figure 6. By combining the scale and squareness errors into a matrix A , the coordinates resulting of point i from the systematic measurement error introduced by the CMM can be calculated using the matrix

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} (1 + S_p)/\cos(S_{pq}) & 0 \\ (1 + S_q)\tan(S_{pq}) & 1 + S_q \end{pmatrix} \approx \begin{pmatrix} 1 + S_p & 0 \\ (1 + S_p)S_{pq} & 1 + S_q \end{pmatrix}. \quad (41)$$

$$(42)$$

The first approximately equal sign holds in the case $|S_{pq}| \ll 1$ in which case $\cos(S_{pq}) \approx 1$ and $\tan(S_{pq}) \approx S_{pq}$. As the CMM's scale errors and squareness

error are usually very small, this linearisation can usually be performed without any significant consequence for the numerical results computed later on.

In addition, the CMM has independent Gaussian random measurement errors ('measurement noise') $\epsilon_{p,i}$ and $\epsilon_{q,i}$ for each measured coordinate with variance σ^2 . In total, the point i with true coordinates $(P_{\text{true},i}, Q_{\text{true},i})$ has the following measured coordinate values $(X_{i,1}, X_{i,2}) = (P_{\text{meas},i}, Q_{\text{meas},i})$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} X_{i,1} \\ X_{i,2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} P_{\text{meas},i} \\ Q_{\text{meas},i} \end{pmatrix} = A \begin{pmatrix} P_{\text{true},i} \\ Q_{\text{true},i} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{x,i} \\ \epsilon_{y,i} \end{pmatrix} \quad (43)$$

Note that if the values of Φ_{lob} ⁴ and Φ_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) are known, then the transformation of $(P_{\text{cen}}, Q_{\text{cen}}, A)$ to the data points $(X_{ij}$ ($1 \leq i \leq n$, $1 \leq j \leq 2$)) is a linear mapping when we disregard the measurement noise. However, the inverse mapping is not straightforward in practice, as in practice the values of Φ_{lob} and Φ_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) are unknown and need to be inferred from the data themselves. The matrix A depends on these values. So in general, the mapping is a non-linear mapping.

An example of simulated coordinates of a circle with three lobes and random noise generated by the VE for the CMM is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Example of simulated measured coordinates of a circle with three lobes and random noise, as generated by the VE for the CMM.

⁴By writing the lobes as sum of sine and cosine function with both an amplitude, knowledge of Φ_{lob} is not required to make the transformation linear.

5.2. Uncertainty evaluation methods

In section 3 various uncertainty methods have been described. We will not repeat their description here, but present the results of various methods. We hereby closely follow [71] and [72].

Two different data analysis methods were studied. As a first step, a Gaussian filter was applied to reduce the impact of measurement noise, equal for both methods. As a second step two different methods to determine the best fit circle have been studied: least-squares optimization and minimum-zone or Chebyshev optimization. From this fit, the radius was derived as well as the roundness value which equals the peak-to-valley difference of the fit residuals.

In figure 8 a typical result for the obtained probability distributions for the radius using the different uncertainty evaluation methods is shown (using least-squares optimization), and similarly figure 9 shows a typical result for the obtained probability distributions for the roundness using different uncertainty evaluation methods.

Figure 8: Probability distributions of the radius for the different uncertainty evaluation methods and least-squares optimization, for a particular sample. (Source: [71], CC BY 4.0).

As the goal of a VE is to accurately simulate the entire measurement process and as in a VE a ground truth value is present given by Y , it is a natural choice to evaluate the performance of the data analysis and uncertainty evaluation methods in terms of their success-rates, based on a large number n_{sim} of repeated simulations, in which both the ground true values of the measurands vary as well as the realizations of the instrument errors and the measurement noise. The success rate $S_{k,m}$ for an uncertainty evaluation method k and measurand Y_m is defined as

$$S_{k,m} = \frac{1}{n_{\text{sim}}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{sim}}} \mathbf{1}(q_{m,i}^{2.5\%} \leq y_{\text{true},m,i} \leq q_{m,i}^{97.5\%}) \quad (44)$$

where $q_{m,i}^{\alpha}$ denotes the α -quantile of the probability distribution calculated using

Figure 9: Probability distributions of the peak-to-valley for the different uncertainty evaluation methods and minimum zone optimization, for a particular sample. (Source: [71], CC BY 4.0).

method m in repetition i , $y_{\text{true},m,i}$ is the true value of measurand m in repetition i , and $\mathbf{1}(A)$ denotes the indicator function for the event A ⁵.

As can be seen in table 3, all methods perform similarly well for the estimation of the radius. However for the roundness there are large differences. Both the methods LPU and PoD (VE cor) have proper success rates, whereas the success rates of the PoD (pert) and PoD (VE) methods is extremely low.

5.3. Alternative modelling choices and uncertainty evaluation procedures

There are more possible variations when using a VE than presented in table 3. We will discuss some further possibilities in this section. These differences are in particular relevant for cases for which the calculated uncertainty differs between the different methods, like for the roundness evaluation.

5.3.1. Type of input data

As mentioned in section 5.1, one may operate the VCMM using a perfect circle corresponding to nominal data, using a simulated imperfect circle or using measurement data. It was already shown in [48] that this choice can significantly impact the calculated uncertainty. Ideally, the true artefact shape is used in the VE, but that is unknown. Instead of that, either the noisy measurement data or realistically simulated non-ideal data containing form deviations can be used. Realistic parameter values for such simulated form deviations can be derived from an initial analysis of the measurement data, from specifications by the manufacturer or from expert knowledge, if available.

⁵ $\mathbf{1}(A)$ is equal to 1 if A is true and 0 otherwise.

Table 3: Coverage percentages of the different uncertainty evaluation methods: Law of Propagation of Uncertainty (LPU), PoD via perturbed data (PoD (pert)), PoD via virtual experiment (PoD (VE)), and PoD via virtual experiment with correction (PoD (VE cor)). The results are shown for both least-squares and minimum zone optimization, and for both radius and roundness. (Adjusted from [71] CC BY 4.0.)

Circle fit optimization method	Uncertainty evaluation method	Radius - success rate	Roundness - success rate
Least-squares	LPU	96 %	90 %
Least-squares	PoD (pert)	95 %	0 %
Least-squares	PoD (VE)	95 %	1 %
Least-squares	PoD (VE cor)	95 %	95 %
Minimum zone	LPU	99 %	94 %
Minimum zone	PoD (pert)	96 %	0 %
Minimum zone	PoD (VE)	95 %	15 %
Minimum zone	PoD (VE cor)	94 %	97 %

5.3.2. Choice of estimate and re-centering of probability distributions

In the methods PoD (pert) and PoD (VE) methods, the probability distribution for the measurand was directly based on the Monte Carlo samples. Alternatively, and what is more commonly done in practice when employing VCMs, the distributions from PoD (pert) and PoD (VE) can be used to calculate the uncertainty only. Mathematically, this can be interpreted as a translation of the distribution such that mean equals a set value. This set value usually corresponds to the value obtained by applying the data analysis function to the measurement data. If that is done for the methods PoD (pert) and PoD (VE) presented in table 3, the success rate increases, but do not attain 95 %. In table 4 the results for these modified methods PoD (pert trans) and PoD (VE trans) are shown for a similar case as presented in section 5.1, see also [72].

5.3.3. Explicit fitting of the artefact imperfections

Another important choice to consider is how the data evaluation is performed. In the standard ISO 12181 [36, 37], the roundness is defined as the residual deviations of the data with respect to a fitted reference circle. However, if a parametrized model is available that is able to correctly model the artefact imperfections and the statistical nature of the measurements, one can also directly use such a model to fit the data. This was done in [72], where instead of fitting a pure circle to the data, the lobed circle of section 5.1 was fitted to the data, which were themselves generated using the same model. The average length of the 95 % coverage intervals and the success rates of the uncertainty evaluation methods for this case are shown in table 5. It can be seen that all methods have now success rates close to 95 % for both radius and roundness with a much lower uncertainty for the roundness than in table 4. However, fitting such a model is not in line with ISO 12181, which is

Table 4: Average length of 95 % coverage intervals and long-run success rates of the different uncertainty evaluation methods when fitting a perfect circle to the data as in ISO 12181. Employed methods are: Law of Propagation of Uncertainty (LPU), PoD via perturbed data followed by a translation of the distribution (PoD (pert trans)), PoD via virtual experiment followed by a translation of the distribution (PoD (VE trans)), and PoD via virtual experiment with correction (PoD (VE cor)). The results are shown for least-squares optimization for both the radius and the roundness. (Adjusted from [72], CC BY 4.0.)

Uncertainty evaluation method	Radius - Average length 95 % coverage interval / mm	Radius - Long-run success rate	Roundness - Average length 95 % coverage interval / mm	Roundness - Long-run success rate
LPU	0.017	94.6 %	0.028	89.1 %
PoD (pert trans)	0.017	94.7 %	0.022	63.3 %
PoD (VE trans)	0.017	94.8 %	0.017	36.2 %
PoD (VE cor)	0.017	94.6 %	0.017	93.3 %
Bayes	0.015	94.8 %	0.002	0.0 %

broadly used in industry. In practice, such a high-quality model for the artefact imperfections may not be available, or it will contain so many parameters that it will become difficult to determine the best fit to the data, and to separate form deviations from instrument related measurement uncertainty.

5.3.4. Bayesian methods

A Bayesian method was also implemented, see again [72]. It turned out that the Bayesian method performed well for estimating the radius, but it was not able to provide a proper estimate of the roundness value in the case the correct statistical model for the data was unknown, as shown in the bottom row of table 4. When the correct statistical model for the data, which included a low-order parametrization of the true form deviation, is available, then the Bayesian method performed well as shown in the bottom row of table 5.

As a low-order parametrization of the true form deviation is usually not known, it can not be advised to use the studied Bayesian method for the VE for the CMM. Using a generic high order parametrization is computationally too expensive and may not converge to the correct solution either. Such a model may be underdetermined and have difficulties correctly separating form deviations from instrument related measurement uncertainty.

Also note that Bayesian methods are difficult to apply when the statistical measurement noise is not additive, but affects the measurement in a complex way. E.g., when the model contains products of random contributions (e.g., translations and rotations related to vibrations) at a low level inside the model. In such a case, the likelihood may not have a simple analytical expression, and solving the Bayesian model risks to become computationally prohibitively expensive if no approximations are used.

Table 5: Average length of 95 % coverage intervals and long-run success rates of the different uncertainty evaluation methods when the correct model - a lobed circle - is fitted to the data. Employed methods: Law of Propagation of Uncertainty (LPU), PoD via perturbed data followed by a translation of the distribution (PoD (pert trans)), PoD via virtual experiment followed by a translation of the distribution (PoD (VE trans)), and PoD via virtual experiment with correction (PoD (VE cor)). The results are shown for least-squares optimization for both the radius and the roundness. (adjusted from [72], CC BY 4.0)

Uncertainty evaluation method	Radius - Average length 95 % coverage interval / mm	Radius - Long-run success rate	Roundness - Average length 95 % coverage interval / mm	Roundness - Long-run success rate
LPU	0.017	94.6 %	0.003	94.0 %
PoD (pert trans)	0.017	94.7 %	0.003	93.9 %
PoD (VE trans)	0.017	94.8 %	0.003	94.1 %
PoD (VE cor)	0.017	94.6 %	0.003	94.4 %
Bayes	0.015	95.0 %	0.003	93.7 %

5.4. GUM-compliance

GUM-compliance is a difficult matter. At a high-level all uncertainty evaluation methods presented in this GPG consider a measurement model, assign uncertainties to the inputs and propagate the uncertainty through the model to the output variables and assign an uncertainty to the measurand. In this sense, all methods are GUM-compliant, and the GUM may allow for different solutions.

Writing the measurand explicitly as function of all input quantities can be very hard to do for complex VEs, and even if possible, multiple solutions may exist, resulting in different uncertainties. These uncertainties may then be GUM-compliant in a stricter sense. However, when arguing that explicit model inversion is required for applying the GUM properly, the GUM can be hard to apply in some situations. Furthermore, the difference between various methods can be small, although non-zero. In [46], we show how large this difference can be for specifically designed worst-case scenarios. However, for well-behaved measurands the difference may be negligible compared to the uncertainty of the input parameters or the model uncertainty.

In this chapter of the GPG we do not advocate or prefer any specific interpretation of GUM-compliance, or the GUM-suite of documents.

5.5. Recommendations and lessons learnt

We finish this section on the CMM case study with some lessons learnt and associated recommendations:

1. In the case of rather smooth measurands, like the radius of a circle, the parameter estimation and uncertainty evaluation is relative insensitive to the employed method. So simple methods can be used.

2. In this GPG, a VE is of the form $\mathbf{X} = g(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{Z})$. In literature, models of the form $\mathbf{X} = \tilde{g}(\mathbf{X}_{in}, \mathbf{Z})$ seem also to be considered as VCMM. Sometimes, even constructions of the form $\mathbf{Y} = \check{g}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}_{in}, \mathbf{Z})$ seem to be regarded as VCMM, i.e., a function that takes measurement data, nominal data and uncertainty sources as input and results in an estimate and uncertainty for the measurand. The reader should be aware of these distinctions when reading the scientific literature and this GPG.
3. The difference between applying perturbations to the true artefact shape coordinates as to simulate measurement errors, and the application of possible corrections for measurement errors to measurement data is also not always carefully considered in literature. Only in the case of symmetric distribution centred around zero there is no difference in the result. Fortunately, this case is the most prevalent one.
4. For VCMMs of the form $\mathbf{X} = \tilde{g}(\mathbf{X}_{in}, \mathbf{Z})$ taking coordinate data as input, use actual coordinates rather than nominal coordinates as input as the calculated uncertainty can significantly depend on small changes in the input data. Actual coordinates, though affected by measurement errors, are expected to be closer to the real artefact shape than nominal data. Alternatively, the VCMM can be repeatedly applied using data based on some realistically simulated form deviations.
5. Determine biases in the data analysis method using the VE and either correct the estimate for biases or enlarge the uncertainty by (linearly) adding the absolute value of the bias to the uncertainty. Do not neglect significant biases, as otherwise the success rate of the calculated coverage interval can be considerably lower than anticipated.
6. If no reliable low-order model for the imperfect object shape is available, do not use Bayesian methods, as it may lead to unrealistically low uncertainties. Bayesian methods require the usage of the correct statistical model.
7. The definition of GUM-compliance of a method is a delicate issue. In a loose sense all proposed methods - although giving different results - may be seen as GUM-compliant, as they propagate input uncertainties through a mathematical model to the output variables. The results from the methods start to differ when uncompensated biases and/or higher order effects come into play. In a strict sense, one might require the analytical or numerical comparison of the method results with the results for an equivalent explicit model of the form $\mathbf{Y} = f(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z})$. However, such a model may be hard or impractical to compute in practice for complex models⁶.

As a pragmatic alternative to strict GUM-compliance, statistical success rates of uncertainty evaluation methods can be calculated, as was done in this section of the GPG. This is common practice in classical statistics and statistical modelling, but this cannot be seen as a criterion for GUM-compliance.

⁶In the presented simplified VE for a CMM, inversion with respect to \mathbf{Z} is actually straightforward.

Table 6: Parameters used in the flow application. (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

Quantity	Value	Unit	Remark
X	-	m/s	Path velocity v_{path} provided from experiment or VE
Y	-	-	Reynolds number Re provided as estimate or from DA
Z_0	0.1	m	Inner pipe diameter D of test rig
Z_1	0.8×10^{-6}	m^2/s	Kinematic viscosity ν of water at $T = 30^\circ$
Z_2	1.425	-	Normalized curvature radius R_c/D of test rig
Z_3	35.49	-	Normalized downstream distance z/D at test rig
Z_4	0	-	Normalized distance between two bends d_l/D at test rig
Z_5	18	$^\circ$	Angular orientation φ of the meter with respect to the upstream bend
k	-	-	Fluid mechanical calibration factor
u_x	-	m/s	Uncertainty in X
u_{z_0}	0.0005	m	Uncertainty in Z_0
u_{z_1}	0	m^2/s	Uncertainty in Z_1
u_{z_2}	0	-	Uncertainty in Z_2
u_{z_3}	0.05	-	Uncertainty in Z_3
u_{z_4}	0	-	Uncertainty in Z_4
u_{z_5}	3	$^\circ$	Uncertainty in Z_5
u_k	0	-	Uncertainty in k

6. Example 3: Uncertainty evaluation for flow measurement

6.1. The virtual flow meter

As stated in Subsection 2.4, in flow metrology, VEs are used to simulate how the flow measurement is influenced by disturbed flow conditions. For this, the entire physical system is modeled in a VE, applying the measurement principle to the calculated flow field. By comparing this virtually determined flow rate with the actual flow rate, an estimate of the fluid-mechanical calibration factor is provided. In the following paragraphs, we will formally introduce the model for the measurand, the DA, the VE, as well as the calibration model (CA) and the calibration model using a VE (CAVE) as this will help us to apply the uncertainty evaluation methods from Section 3 to the virtual flow meter. The notation follows [7], where also further details can be found.

Table 6, taken from [7], summarizes the relevant parameters for the virtual flow meter. Furthermore, the values of these parameters that are used in the example in Paragraph 6.2.3 are given.

6.1.1. Model for the measurand

The model for the measurand describes the functional relationship between the measurand, i.e., the quantity to be measured, and all known input quantities. According to the notation used in [7], the measurand, i.e., the quantity of interest, in the flow application is the Reynolds number, which is a dimensionless representation of the flow rate Q . Furthermore, the model for the measurand will, according to the notation of [51, 71], also be denoted as the DA, motivated by statistical inference that has to be applied for a flow measurement. While the DA models the functional relationship between the measurand and its affecting input quantities, the VE produces observations of the measured quantity, given specific values for

Figure 10: Flow chart of the DA representing the experimental flow measurement. (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

the measurand and the additional input quantities.

6.1.2. DA

The DA aims to experimentally determine the measurand Y with the installed flow meter. For the flow meter, the DA is given by

$$Y = f(X, \mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, k), \quad (45)$$

where X is the measured quantity, i.e., the path velocity, and $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1} = (Z_0, Z_1)$ and k are the input quantities. The function f is given by

$$f(X, \mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, k) = k X \frac{Z_0}{Z_1}, \quad (46)$$

where Z_0 is the inner diameter of the pipe, Z_1 is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid and k is the fluid mechanical calibration factor, see Table 6 for more details. The algorithm for the experimental flow measurement, i.e., the DA, is shown in Figure 10.

6.1.3. VE

The VE is a virtual realization of a measurement process that makes it possible to generate virtual observations of a quantity that would also be observed in a real measurement. The VE of the flow meter is symbolized by

$$X_{VE} = g(Y, \mathbf{Z}_{2,3,4,5}), \quad (47)$$

where X_{VE} is the virtually measured path velocity, Y is the measurand, and $\mathbf{Z}_{2,3,4,5}$ are the flow input quantities, which include the geometrical parameters and fluid properties of the considered configuration that affect the measurement. A detailed breakdown of the quantities, their values and associated uncertainties can be found in Table 6. Further, Figure 11 illustrates the algorithm for the virtual flow measurement, i.e., the VE.

Figure 11: Flow chart of the VE representing the virtual flow measurement. (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

Figure 12: Flow chart of the CA representing the experimental determination of the fluid mechanical calibration factor. (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

6.1.4. CA

The CA determines the fluid mechanical calibration factor k experimentally. In addition to the previously introduced quantities, this approach requires the knowledge of a reference flow rate Q_{ref} , from which the reference Reynolds number Y_{ref} is determined straightforwardly by using the following formula:

$$Y_{\text{ref}} = \frac{Q_{\text{ref}} Z_0}{A Z_1}, \quad (48)$$

where Z_0 denotes the inner diameter of the pipe, $A = \pi (Z_0/2)^2$ its cross-sectional area and Z_1 the kinematic viscosity of the fluid. Suppose the reference flow rate Q_{ref} as well as the viscosity of the fluid Z_1 and the inner pipe diameter Z_0 are given. In that case, the fluid mechanical calibration factor can be determined analytically as

$$k = h(X, Y_{\text{ref}}, Z_{0,1}), \quad (49)$$

where the function h is given by

$$h(X, Y_{\text{ref}}, Z_{0,1}) = \frac{Y_{\text{ref}} Z_1}{X Z_0}. \quad (50)$$

The implementation of the CA follows the algorithm shown in Figure 12.

6.1.5. CAVE

If the reference flow rate Q_{ref} is not given, the CAVE model can be used instead. In this case, the fluid mechanical calibration factor is determined by a VE, which is, in the case of a flow meter, usually based on CFD simulations. In this GPG, we follow the approach described in [7] and use the surrogate model from [77] as the VE model to determine the fluid mechanical calibration factor. In this approach, the fluid mechanical calibration factor k is written as the product of two components: $k = k_u k_d$, where k_u represents the calibration factor for undisturbed, fully developed turbulent flow and k_d represents the one for specific flow disturbances. Please note that, according to [77], only the undisturbed component k_u depends on the actual Reynolds number. It is calculated as follows:

$$k_u = \frac{1}{g_u(Y, \mathbf{Z}_{2,3,4,5})} \frac{Y Z_1}{Z_0} = \frac{1}{X_u} \frac{Y Z_1}{Z_0}, \quad (51)$$

where g_u denotes the function, with which the undisturbed part of the path velocity (denoted by X_u) is determined. In the CAVE algorithm, this component is iteratively adjusted until the predicted Reynolds number aligns with the measured path velocity X . In contrast, the disturbed component k_d is determined only once, based on an initially estimated Reynolds number Y_0 and the given input quantities \mathbf{Z} :

$$k_d = \frac{g_u(Y, \mathbf{Z}_{2,3,4,5})}{g(Y, \mathbf{Z}_{2,3,4,5})} = \frac{X_u}{X_{\text{VE}}}. \quad (52)$$

For further details, the reader is referred to [7]. The schematic sequence of the CAVE algorithm and its iterative adjustment is shown in Figure 13.

6.2. Uncertainty evaluation methods applied to the virtual flow meter

6.2.1. LPU

In the following, the LPU methods described in Subsection 3.2 will be applied to the virtual flow meter. First, the implementation of the LPU using the DA will be outlined. Note that, for the flow application, the path velocity X , the Reynolds number Y and the fluid mechanical calibration factor k are univariate. However, the input quantity $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ is multivariate and $u_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}$ denotes the vector of uncertainties for the individual quantities, i.e., no correlations are considered here. According to the LPU, the uncertainty of the measurand Y is given by

$$u_Y = \left(J^f U (J^f)^T \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (53)$$

where J^f denotes the Jacobian of the evaluation function f and $U = \text{diag}(u_X^2, u_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}^2, u_k^2)$ is the diagonal covariance matrix of the measured and input quantities. For illustration, Figure 14 presents a flowchart for implementing the LPU using the DA.

Note that this method can only be used if the value of the fluid mechanical calibration factor k and its associated uncertainty are given, e.g., if they have been determined beforehand by comparing the measured flow rate with a reference flow rate. Otherwise, a VE has to be used to determine the fluid mechanical calibration factor iteratively. In this case, the LPU approach is extended by including a VE.

Figure 13: Flow chart of the CAVE representing the virtual determination of the fluid dynamical calibration factor. (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

This extension of the LPU approach is used if the fluid mechanical calibration factor k and its associated uncertainty are unknown. In particular, it is assumed that the CAVE algorithm as described in Paragraph 6.1.5 is performed. Since the CAVE is given by an implicit function, appropriate uncertainty evaluation procedures are required. In the following, we apply the approach presented in supplement 2 of the GUM [43], where the implicit function theorem is utilized to obtain a formulation similar to the LPU. In particular, once an estimate for the involved quantities is determined, the uncertainty for the measurand Y is evaluated according to

$$u_Y = \left(J_Y^{-1} J_{X,Z} U (J_{X,Z})^T J_Y^{-T} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (54)$$

where J_Y and $J_{X,Z}$ are the respective partial derivatives of the implicit function $m(X, Y, \mathbf{Z})$, evaluated at the corresponding estimates. As previously stated with a slight modification in the notation of \mathbf{Z} , the matrix U describes the covariance matrix of the variables X and \mathbf{Z} .

The following scheme illustrates how the LPU using a VE-DA combination can be implemented.

Figure 15 illustrates how the LPU using the VE-DA combination can be imple-

Figure 14: Schematic overview of LPU using DA. (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

mented. Detailed step-by-step instructions can be found in [7].

6.2.2. PoD

In the following, we apply the PoD method to the DA. In this approach, the uncertainty of the measurand Y is characterized by a state-of-knowledge probability distribution P_Y , which incorporates the uncertainties of the involved measured quantity X and the input quantities $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k through the function $f(X, \mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, k)$. The uncertainties in X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k are modeled by their respective state-of-knowledge probability distributions P_X , $P_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}$ and P_k , respectively. In the following, all of these distributions are assumed to follow a normal distribution.

Assuming a normal distribution for the involved input quantities requires specification of their mean and standard deviation. Since k is either already known (e.g., in terms of a look-up table or expert knowledge) or determined beforehand by the CA model function h , its mean k is treated as a given input quantity alongside its associated uncertainty u_k within the method. Similarly, for the input quantities $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$, a mean (using the same symbol) and a covariance matrix $u_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}^2$ are assigned from expert knowledge. For the measured quantity X , the measurement is taken as the mean of P_X and u_X^2 denotes the assigned variance, which is taken from repeated measurements and assumed to be known.

The distribution P_Y is generated by repeatedly sampling values $x_n \sim P_X$, $\mathbf{z}_n \sim P_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}$ and $k_n \sim P_k$ and then evaluating them with the function $f(X, \mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, k)$ as

$$y_n = f(x_n, \mathbf{z}_n, k_n). \quad (55)$$

The resulting y_n values form a sample of the distribution P_Y . This approach effectively describes the propagation of uncertainty by propagating the distributions

Figure 15: Schematic overview of LPU using the VE-DA combination. (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

P_X , $P_{Z_{0,1}}$ and P_k through the function $f(X, Z_{0,1}, k)$ to determine the distribution P_Y of the output quantity Y . To obtain an estimate \hat{Y} for the measurand Y and its uncertainty u_Y , the mean and standard deviation of the sample (y_1, \dots, y_N) are calculated:

$$\hat{Y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N y_n, \quad (56)$$

$$u_Y = \left(\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{n=1}^N (y_n - \hat{Y})^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (57)$$

The schematic overview for implementing the PoD applied to DA is illustrated in Figure 16. A more detailed description of the algorithm can be found in [7].

Next, the PoD method is applied to the VE, followed by the DA. In this approach, in contrast to the PoD applied to the DA approach above, the uncertainty in k is not a priori represented by a probability distribution. Instead, k is calculated from x_n and z_n at each sampling step with the CAVE model, see Paragraph 6.1.5. Since k is calculated iteratively from the measured quantity X , input quantities Z and an initial estimate of the measurand Y_0 for each sample drawing within the CAVE, the probability distribution of k is actually an intermediate result that is subsequently propagated through the model for the measurand f . The

Figure 16: Schematic overview of PoD applied to DA. (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

distribution P_Y is generated by first sampling $x_n \sim P_X$ and $z_n \sim P_{Z_{0,1}}$ and then calculating the corresponding value of k_n using the CAVE algorithm. The final output y_n is obtained by evaluating the function $f(x_n, z_n, k_n)$ as stated in Eq. (55). The resulting values y_n form a sample of the distribution P_Y . This method effectively describes the propagation of uncertainty by considering the independent distributions P_X and $P_{Z_{0,1}}$, along with the deterministic calculation of k processed through the function $f(X, Z_{0,1}, k)$. With the distribution P_Y , the measurand Y is defined by its mean and the associated uncertainty u_Y is represented by the standard deviation. Hence, they can be calculated with Eqs. (56)+(57). Even though a VE and numerical optimization, i.e., a fixed-point iteration, are applied within the estimation of the measurand, this procedure can be seen as in line with the uncertainty evaluation framework of supplement 1 of the GUM [41]. For a detailed description of the implementation of this scheme, the reader is referred to [7]. Its visualization can be found in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Schematic overview of PoD applied to VE, followed by DA. (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

6.2.3. Results and discussion

In the following, we summarize the results from three of the case studies presented in [7]. The aim of this paragraph is to show how the different methods introduced above can be applied in flow applications. For this, we consider the flow field downstream of a single elbow (SE), a double S-elbow (DSE), and a double elbow out-of-plane (DE) at a Reynolds number of 5×10^4 . The considered geometries are shown in Figure 18. The selected input values are summarized in Table 6.

In the proposed framework, the uncertainty for k is assumed to be zero under the premise that it can be measured with sufficient precision in the flow meter benchmark application. This assumption also reflects the conditions that are assumed for the VE, namely that it is exact, i.e., without any errors. Hence, this simplification allows a direct comparison between the experimental and virtual determination of the fluid mechanical calibration factors since the same measured and input quantities with their associated uncertainties impact the evaluation methods.

In the following, the performance of the different uncertainty evaluation methods introduced above are evaluated, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the

Figure 18: Left: single elbow (SE), middle: double S-elbow (DSE), right: double elbow out-of-plane (DE). (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

Figure 19: Confidence intervals for the measurand (i.e., the Reynolds number) for the four different uncertainty evaluation methods (light green: LPU applied to DA, dark green: LPU applied to VE-DA, light purple: PoD applied to DA, dark pink: PoD applied to VE-DA) and corresponding reference value (red dashed line) for the three considered geometries at a Reynolds number of 5×10^4 . (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

influences of the various measured and input quantities on the measurand Y and its uncertainty u_Y . The results are verified by comparison with a reference value for each case.

The uncertainties of the methods are taken into account in the form of confidence intervals with upper bounds CI_{upper} and lower bounds CI_{lower} , given as $Y_{cal} \pm k_{CI} u_Y$ with $k_{CI} = 1.96$ corresponding to 95% coverage under the assumption of a normal distribution. It was found that the reference value for the measurand Y_{ref} lies within these uncertainty intervals in all cases. This indicates that none of the methods show systematic deviations regarding the uncertainty evaluation. The results are visualized in Figure 19 using an error bar plot to illustrate the calculated measurand Y_{cal} together with its uncertainty u_Y as calculated by the different methods. Further, a dashed red line shows the reference value Y_{ref} . The figure shows that the results of the methods differ only slightly.

In detail, a slight trend within the deviation is apparent. The VE-DA methods, which include the virtual determination of the fluid mechanical calibration factors, tend to have slightly higher uncertainties than the DA methods. This can

Table 7: Results for the double elbow out-of-plane configuration for a Reynolds number of 5×10^4 . (Source: [7], CC BY 4.0).

Method	Y_{ref} [-]	Y_{cal} [-]	u_Y [-]	CI_{lower} [-]	CI_{upper} [-]	time / s	Sample Size
LPU applied to DA	50078.806	50078.806	250.823	49587.193	50570.418	0.251	1
LPU applied to VE-DA	50078.806	50078.795	258.489	49572.157	50585.434	31.517	1
PoD applied to DA	50078.806	50079.177	251.518	49586.202	50572.152	0.402	10^5
PoD applied to VE-DA	50078.806	50079.062	258.072	49573.240	50584.884	13306.247	10^5

be attributed to the dependence of the virtual frameworks on model assumptions and approximations, which can introduce additional uncertainties. This difference is noticeable for all three geometrical configurations, where the uncertainties obtained by the DA methods consistently show lower overall uncertainties. These findings underscore the inherent influence within the VE-DA methods by numerical errors.

Nevertheless, the overall consistency between the results of the different uncertainty evaluation approaches, see Figure 19, confirms the methods' reliability. The almost identical results of the measurand Y_{cal} compared to the reference measurand value Y_{ref} and minor deviations of the uncertainties u_Y show that all methods suit the analyzed scenarios.

When choosing a suitable uncertainty evaluating method, it is crucial to identify the most suitable approach depending on the specific scenario and given conditions. The choice of method depends heavily on whether k is a known input quantity or needs to be determined virtually. For this, the methods are further investigated for one of the chosen configurations (namely the DE) regarding their performance under the following two distinct scenarios: (1) when k is experimentally given and uncertainty evaluation with DA methods is applicable or (2) when k is not known, which implies the requirement of uncertainty evaluation with VE-DA methods. Table 7 provides an overview of the DE case, including the performance for each method in terms of accuracy, computation time and sample size as key validation metrics. All methods were executed in parallel using 8 logical processors via a multiprocessing pool to provide a comparison of their computational performance. The LPU applied to DA, LPU applied to VE-DA and PoD applied to DA methods were computed on a local PC with an Intel Core i5-10310U processor, featuring 4 physical cores and 8 logical processors. The PoD applied to VE-DA method was parallelized on a workstation with two AMD EPYC 7702 processors, totaling 128 physical cores and 256 logical processors, with computations explicitly limited to 8 logical processors.

For each method, the absolute error

$$E_{\text{abs}} = |Y_{\text{cal}} - Y_{\text{ref}}| \quad (58)$$

and the relative error (in percent)

$$E_{\text{rel}} = \frac{E_{\text{abs}}}{Y_{\text{ref}}} \times 100 \% \quad (59)$$

are calculated.

In scenarios where the LPU and PoD are applied to the DA method, i.e., where the fluid mechanical calibration factor k is determined experimentally, the results show that the LPU achieved perfect accuracy with $E_{\text{abs}} = 0$ and $E_{\text{rel}} = 0 \%$. This was to be expected since LPU requires the fluid mechanical calibration factor to be precisely determined beforehand, ensuring a perfect analytical computation of the output measurand Y . In detail, it means that the input measurand value Y_{ref} of the CA is the output measurand value Y of the LPU method by construction. The PoD applied to DA method produced slightly higher errors of $E_{\text{abs}} = 0.371$ and $E_{\text{rel}} = 7.408 \times 10^{-4} \%$ due to the stochastic nature of Monte Carlo simulations used in PoD. In particular, a sample size of 10^5 leads to differences in the fifth significant digit that may be viewed as random fluctuations. To verify this, an additional analysis using an increased sample size of 10^7 was performed in [7]. This analysis confirmed that the initial discrepancies are due to sampling limitations rather than systematic errors. In terms of computation time, the LPU applied to DA method was very fast, requiring only 0.251 seconds. In this approach, only analytical equations derived from partial derivatives need to be calculated to propagate uncertainties through the model. The LPU applied to DA method avoids the iterative algorithm inherent in the CAVE and stochastic approximations inherent in Monte Carlo simulations, making it computationally highly efficient. The PoD applied to DA method required slightly more time of 0.402 seconds due to the computational cost of Monte Carlo simulations but remained competitive with the LPU applied to DA method.

In scenarios where the fluid mechanical calibration factor k is not known and needs to be determined virtually (e.g., using the CAVE algorithm), the results highlight that the LPU applied to VE-DA method demonstrated a very high accuracy with $E_{\text{abs}} = 0.011$ and $E_{\text{rel}} = 2.197 \times 10^{-5} \%$. The results were close to the LPU applied to DA approach but showed minor deviations due to the inclusion of the VE. The PoD applied to VE-DA method produced a higher absolute error, with $E_{\text{abs}} = 0.256$ and $E_{\text{rel}} = 5.112 \times 10^{-4} \%$. The combination of Monte Carlo sampling and the iterative algorithm of the CAVE introduced a certain level of computational and sampling errors. In terms of computation time, the LPU applied to VE-DA method is computationally efficient and, hence, practically applicable, taking 31.517 seconds. In contrast, the PoD applied to VE-DA method was very slow with a computation time of approximately 3.7 hours. The combination of Monte Carlo sampling and iterative VE-DA algorithms significantly increases computational demands. However, it is a versatile tool for nonlinear systems and cases with non-Gaussian distributions, making it applicable across a wide range of application scenarios.

The observed trends align with theoretical expectations. VE-DA methods inherently involve iterative algorithms, which require more computation time. Still, VE-DA methods are needed if the fluid mechanical calibration factor is not given. While Monte Carlo simulations are computationally intensive due to the need for large sample sizes to approximate the uncertainty with high precision, they remain advantageous for complex, nonlinear systems where traditional LPU methods are usually not applicable. In contrast, LPU leverages deterministic equations, making it faster and more accurate for problems with well-defined linear relationships. However, approximations of the sensitivity coefficients have to be taken into ac-

count, e.g., when computing a numerical gradient of the VE. Overall, practical scenarios and conditions influence the method selection significantly.

7. Recommendations and Conclusion

In this GPG, the usage of VEs in metrology has been discussed for the purpose of uncertainty evaluation. With a definition of VEs as representations of a real measurement, this GPG presents various methods for uncertainty evaluation in relation to VEs in conjunction with real measurement data. In practice, these methods often need adaptation to the specific use-case and several additional challenges arise. We showed how to evaluate the measurement uncertainty for three use-cases coming from tilted-wave interferometry, coordinate metrology and flow measurement.

It is natural that this GPG can not cover all aspects of virtual metrology that are important for a successful uncertainty evaluation. In particular, this guide assumes a fixed VE without any updating or iterative calibration mechanism. For this we refer to the accompanying guide on Digital Twins. Also, no discussion regarding the quality of a VE is performed. A non-perfect VE may introduce additional uncertainty sources that needs to be accounted for. In this case, we refer the reader to another accompanying guide on validation and surrogate modelling.

When it comes to explicit recommendations, the following rules should be considered with cautiousness and may not always be applicable. Nevertheless, during the research on the use-cases considered in this GPG and while writing this document, some context specific practical rules have been identified.

If a measurement function is available and all its quantities are known, the usual GUM uncertainty evaluation framework for LPU 3.2.1 or PoD 3.3.1 can be used, also as a reference procedure.

If a VE is used to define a measurement function, for instance in a least-squares sense, the extensions to LPU 3.2.2 and PoD 3.3.2 accounting for the VE can be considered. Also here, the LPU approaches relies on a linearity assumption. While this property can be justified in many cases, since one is only usually interested in a small parameter region, it is not be applicable in general. There are tests for linearity, also given in the GUM, which can be applied before relying on this approach. In the use-cases analysed in this GPG and within the simplifications considered, the TWI application in Section 4.2 and FLOW application in Section 6.2.1 yield adequate results using these linear approaches. However, some elements of the CMM application have been identified in Section 5.5 that may not be reasonably analysed using these approaches.

The PoD methods that are usually implemented using MC sampling are generally able to account for non-linearities. However, some variants of these approaches may be more suitable than others. In particular, when estimates are taken as intermediate results, for instance in the approach of Section 3.3.2, many different approaches can be identified to include the VE. Some of these may introduce a bias in the resulting estimate, which may also affect the resulting uncertainty for non-linear dependencies.

In the case of VEs, a rather natural approach for uncertainty evaluation is the Bayesian method of Section 3.4. Since a VE already models observations, the

general form of a VE can directly be used. While the construction of suitable likelihood functions from a VE may be challenging and the assignment of reasonable state-of-knowledge distributions may not always be straight forward, the Bayesian approach offers several advantages. The inclusion of prior knowledge regarding the measurement instrument or the measurand itself are key aspects of a Bayesian inference.

It is the authors hope that this GPG provides the reader with sufficient information and inspiration to be able to evaluate the uncertainty of its own complex measurements with the help of a VE.

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A. Simplified virtual experiment and uncertainty evaluation methods for the TWI

The following pages are taken from a Matlab[®] live script that implements the numerics corresponding to Section 4.2.

Simplified virtual experiment (benchmark scenario) and estimation methods

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Preliminary remarks

The following development implements a **simplified**, i.e., linearized variant of the tilted-wave interferometer (TWI) and prepares uncertainty evaluation for this simplified model. Moreover, important concepts, such as model correction and post-processing of the form reconstruction result obtained (reconstruction of higher spatial frequencies and position and orientation correction of the surface under test) are not performed in this study. This means, the measurand of this simplified model differs from the measurand of the real TWI, and **the results obtained here are not representative for the quality of the actual TWI** and the obtained uncertainties may differ significantly to those obtained in the real experiment. It is to note that here and in the following, when referring to the TWI, the simplified and linearized version is considered.

Introduction

In this notebook, a benchmark scenario is developed that applies the concepts of the simplified TWI in a simple and numerically efficient way to define a virtual experiment. For that, a linearization of the TWI is considered that has been generated from analytical and numerical derivatives of the actual TWI simulation model. The combination of this linear simulation (or forward) model with a simple additive Gaussian noise assumption, provides the virtual experiment under consideration for this task.

This document introduces only the employed VE and provides an estimation strategy for the underlying measurand. Other documents will use these concepts for uncertainty evaluation.

The virtual experiment (VE) for the benchmark scenario

The considered virtual experiment is of the following form

$$x^{ve} = G(y, z, \epsilon) \approx A[y, z] + \epsilon = A_y y + A_z z + \epsilon, \quad \epsilon \text{ realization of } E \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I).$$

Here, the matrix A has the size of $n \times p$, with $n \gg p$ and it is the result of the linearization from the complex TWI chosen for a specific realistic scenario, without further details. The actual VE \mathcal{G} is hence approximated by the corresponding linear function and Gaussian measurement noise model. The sub-matrices A_y and A_z correspond to

different parameter influences. y represent values for Y , which denotes the measurand. Similarly, z represent realizations of Z , which is a multivariate parameter with Type-B information whose true value is generally unknown and which represents the physical setup of the experiment, e.g. positions and orientations of optical lenses within the TWI. The statistical fluctuation of repeated measurements are represented by ϵ , which is assumed to follow a Gaussian noise model with known standard deviation $\sigma > 0$. In particular, we consider

Symbol of value	Symbol of Quantity	Quantity description	Distribution	Comment
x^{ve}	X^{ve}	Deviations of optical path differences from a nominal system	Multivariate type A quantity	Abbreviated: OPDDs (optical path difference differences)
y	Y	Parametric description of measurand and position of Surface Under Test (SUT) in x and y direction.	-	Coefficients of Zernike polynomials, Position of SUT in x and y direction
z	Z	Collection of different elements of the VE, each consists of 6 parameters (3 position parameter in m and 3 rotation/orientation parameter in rad): - Zoom Optics - Collimator - Image Optics - Beamsplitter - CCD - Source Plane - Surface Under Test (SUT), but only those which are not in y. Additionally, the wavelength in m is considered.	multivariate Gaussian	Quantities with Type B information
ϵ	E	Measurement noise	multivariate Gaussian	Standard deviation is assumed to be known as $\sigma = 10^{-8}$ m

Note that we write the quantities with upper case letters and specific values for these quantities with lower case letters.

Execute : Setting environment & read input files

The matrices A_Y and A_Z for a specific measurement scenario are provided in the DATA directory and can be loaded using the following commands.

Setting Environment

```
clear all;
addpath ('HELPERS');
fprintf ('\n=====\n Execution at
"%s"\n=====\n', string(datetime));
```

```
=====  
Execution at "09-Apr-2026 10:27:30"
```

```
=====
```

```
specimen_id = 1; case_nr = '0005'; % Toroid (C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom)
% specimen_id = 2; case_nr = '0005'; % glasssphere_r30_THD_1
% specimen_id = 3; case_nr = '0005'; % glasssphere_r30_THD_2
% specimen_id = 4; case_nr = '0005'; % UPOB#4_strongAsphere_2
PATH_DATA = get_path_data (specimen_id);
fprintf ('Environment:\nPATH_DATA = %s\n\n', PATH_DATA);
```

```
Environment:
```

```
PATH_DATA = ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom
```

```
% Reading Sensitivity Files
```

```
J = t_jacs (PATH_DATA, true);
```

```
J.load_all;
```

```
reading all parameters:
```

```
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/pccd.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/img_key.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/rcn.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_rcn.mat ...done (4.07555s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/par_rcn.mat ...done (0.056087s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/bsp.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_bsp.mat ...done (0.120455s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/ccd.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_ccd.mat ...done (0.113799s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/col.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_col.mat ...done (0.117237s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/img.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_img.mat ...done (0.114521s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/src.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_src.mat ...done (0.110084s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/sut.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_sut.mat ...done (0.113166s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/wvl.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_wvl.mat ...done (0.029782s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/zom.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_zom.mat ...done (0.118917s).
```

```
J_SUT = J.get_obj("sut");
```

```
J_SUT.mask_y = [true true false, false, false, false];
```

```
J_SUT.mask_z = ~J_SUT.mask_y;
```

```
A_Y = J.get_jac ('y'); % Operator corresponding to Zernike coefficients & xy parameter
```

```
A_Z = J.get_jac ('z'); % other parameter
```

Measurements (virtual forward simulation)

We consider that a set of measurements from the experiment are given

$$x = (x_1, \dots, x_m),$$

which are realizations of the measured quantity X . For illustration purposes, we consider measurements which are realizations of the VE, that includes all uncertainty contributions, i.e. that corresponds to the X^{ve} that is the output of the VE, i.e., optical path length difference differences (OPDDs). For more details about the actual quantities involved, cf. [Fortmeier2022].

Each quantity as defined in the table above, is assigned an uncertainty. In the following different uncertainties are considered, cf. the cases below in the code:

Execute : Setting uncertainties for parameters

```
J_rcn          = J.get_obj ('rcn');          % sensitivity for zernike coefficients (sut
= surface under test)

switch case_nr
  case '0001'
    sigma       = 10e-9;                    % noise of about 10 nm
    std_ncy     = 0;
    factor_sut  = 1;
    factor_wvl  = 0;
    vec_sut    = factor_sut*[5e-5 5e-5 0e-6, 3e-4 3e-4, 3e-4];
    par_y      = J_rcn.ground_truth_T_DIFF_alpha_nm (J_rcn.mask_y,3); % No uncertainty is
assigned to the Zernike coefficients,...
  case '0002'
    sigma       = 10e-9;
    std_ncy     = 0;
    factor_sut  = 0;
    factor_wvl  = 0;
    vec_sut    = factor_sut*[0 0 0 0 0];
    par_y      = J_rcn.ground_truth_T_DIFF_alpha_nm (J_rcn.mask_y,3);
  case '0003'
    sigma       = 10e-9;
    std_ncy     = 0;
    factor_sut  = 0;
    factor_wvl  = 0;
    vec_sut    = factor_sut*[0 0 0 0 0];
    par_y      = 0;
  case '0004'
    sigma       = 10e-9;
    std_ncy     = 0;
    factor_sut  = 1;
    factor_wvl  = 0;
    vec_sut    = factor_sut*[5e-6 5e-6 1e-6, 3e-4 3e-4, 3e-4];
    par_y      = J_rcn.ground_truth_T_DIFF_alpha_nm (J_rcn.mask_y,3);

  case '0005'
    sigma       = 10e-9;
    std_ncy     = 0;
    factor_sut  = 1;
    factor_wvl  = 0;
    vec_sut    = factor_sut*[5e-7 5e-7 1e-6, 3e-5 3e-5, 3e-5];
    par_y      = J_rcn.ground_truth_T_DIFF_alpha_nm (J_rcn.mask_y,3);
  case 'all'
    sigma       = 10e-9;
    std_ncy     = [3e-6 3e-6 3e-6 3e-4 3e-4 3e-4];
    factor_sut  = 1;
    factor_wvl  = 1;
    vec_sut    = factor_sut*[5e-6 5e-6 1e-6, 3e-4 3e-4, 3e-4];
    par_y      = J_rcn.ground_truth_T_DIFF_alpha_nm (J_rcn.mask_y,3);
```

```

    otherwise
        error ('unknown case_nr %s', case_nr);
end

J_rcn = J.get_obj ('rcn'); % sensitivity for Zernike
coefficients (sut = surface under test)
J.get_obj("rcn").par_y = par_y; % No uncertainty is assigned
to the Zernike coefficients, ...

J.get_obj("bsp").U = std_ucy; % beamsplitter
J.get_obj("ccd").U = std_ucy; % CCD just very small
uncertainty
J.get_obj("col").U = std_ucy; % collimator just very small
uncertainty
J.get_obj("img").U = std_ucy; % image plane just very
small uncertainty
J.get_obj("src").U = std_ucy; % Source plane just very
small uncertainty
J_SUT.U = vec_sut;
J.get_obj("wvl").U = factor_wvl*2.8e-12; % wavelength uncertainty
according to A1.2.1 report
J.get_obj("zom").U = std_ucy; % Zoom objectives, just very
small uncertainty

```

According to the uncertainties assigned above, a random realization is drawn in the following for the quantities Y and Z of the virtual experiment.

Execute : Draw a specific realization for virtual experiment

```

J.set_par_U_rand; % generates a realization
according to uncertainties defined in object
J.disp_par ('y', case_nr);

```

```

=====
case 0005 (y)
=====

rcn : [NaN          NaN          NaN  -4.22524e-09  4.333582e-07  2.661929e-08  1.009117e-08 ...]
bsp : [NaNm NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
ccd : [NaNm NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
col : [NaNm NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
img : [NaNm NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
src : [NaNm NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
sut : [-3.01749e-08m -3.9877e-08m NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
wvl : NaN pm
zom : [NaNm NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]

```

```

J.disp_par ('z', case_nr);

```

```

=====
case 0005 (z)
=====

rcn : [NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN ...]
bsp : [-0m -0m 0m -0rad 0rad -0rad]

```

```

ccd : [0m -0m 0m 0rad 0rad 0rad]
col : [-0m -0m 0m 0rad 0rad -0rad]
img : [0m -0m 0m 0rad 0rad 0rad]
src : [0m 0m 0m 0rad -0rad 0rad]
sut : [NaNm NaNm 1.22271e-06m -1.76828e-05rad 5.13198e-05rad 3.74119e-05rad]
wvl : -0 pm
zom : [-0m -0m -0m -0rad 0rad -0rad]

```

```
% J.disp_par ('c', case_nr);
```

Execute : Simulate forward experiment

```

y_ground_truth = zeros (size (A_Y,2),1); % ground truth, no position errors, sut = design
surface (no difference zenike)
ix_xy = (size(y_ground_truth,1)-sum(J_SUT.mask_y)+1):size(y_ground_truth,1);
ix_ai = 1:(size(y_ground_truth,1)-sum(J_SUT.mask_y));
ai_key = find (J.get_obj("rcn").mask_y);
xy_key = find (J_SUT.mask_y);
n_xy = length(ix_xy);
n_ai = length(ix_ai);

y_ground_truth(ix_xy) = J_SUT.par_y (J_SUT.mask_y);
y_ground_truth(ix_ai) = J_rcn.par_y (J_rcn.mask_y); % some ground truth that we want to
reconstruct later

yzw_realization = J.get_par('a'); % returns current random realization

A = J.get_jac('a'); % returns full matrix A. Columns correspond to sub-
matrices above

OPDD = A * yzw_realization;
OPDD = OPDD + sigma * randn(size(OPDD));

```

Result OPDD on CCD

```

plot_ccd_fwd(J, OPDD); % Plot the data (comma prevents second output of
image in notebook)

```


Example OPDDs that are generated by the benchmark TWI. The root-mean-square value over the 2D plane is given over each image. The four images correspond to a single measurement, since different illumination settings of the specimen are considered. These generated observations are dominated by position effects and would be corrected in a real measurement scenario prior to the reconstruction of the topography (measurement).

The measurement model / data analysis for the benchmark scenario

The choice of the measurement model is generally ambiguous when using a virtual experiment as above. This is, since many measurement models can be derived that correspond to the virtual experiment above, e.g. the choice of estimation parameters is often not uniquely defined.

A common choice for a measurement model that involves the interpretation as a regression model can, due to the linearity of the VE, be written as the solution of a corresponding linear least-squares problem. Since a measurement model is given in terms of quantities and not values, we use here the corresponding upper case letters

$$Y_1 = f_1(X, Z) = \operatorname{argmin}_{\tilde{Y}} \left\| X - (A_y \tilde{Y} + A_z Z) \right\|_2^2.$$

This means, for a specific realization of x and z , the corresponding estimate for Y_1 is given by

$$\hat{Y}_1 = A_Y^\dagger (x - A_Z z),$$

where A_Y^\dagger denotes the pseudo-inverse matrix of A_Y .

It is to mention that the measurement model f_1 is partially inverse to the deterministic part of the VE, i.e. the forward model, if and only if the matrix A_y has full rank. In particular, for some y and z it holds

$$f_1(G(y, z, 0), z) = f_1(A_Y y + A_Z z, z) = A_Y^\dagger (A_Y y + A_Z z - A_Z z) = (A_Y^\dagger A_Y) y.$$

Obtaining estimates for the measurand

For the measurement model that we consider, the estimate can be obtained by simply applying f_1 .

Execute : f1 and plot topography

```
% inverse Matrix
A_Y_p = pinv (A_Y);
% define f1
f1 = @(x_, z_) A_Y_p*(x_ - A_Z*z_);
% execute f1
z_zeros = zeros (size(A_Z,2),1);
hat_y_1 = f1(OPDD, z_zeros);

fig1a = figure;
fontsize = 16;
fig1a.Position = [0 0 2560 1080];
h1 = subplot (1,3,1,'parent', fig1a);
ai_est = hat_y_1(ix_ai);
xlabel(h1, 'X Label', 'FontSize', fontsize)
ylabel(h1, 'Y Label', 'FontSize', fontsize)
plot_topo_ai (h1, J_rcn, ai_est, 'est. diff. topo (z=0)');
h2 = subplot (1,3,2,'parent', fig1a);
xlabel(h2, 'X Label', 'FontSize', fontsize)
ylabel(h2, 'Y Label', 'FontSize', fontsize)
ai_gt = y_ground_truth(ix_ai);
plot_topo_ai (h2, J_rcn, ai_gt, 'ground truth diff. topo');
h3 = subplot (1,3,3,'parent', fig1a);
ai_res = ai_est-ai_gt;
xlabel(h3, 'X Label', 'FontSize', fontsize)
ylabel(h3, 'Y Label', 'FontSize', fontsize)
plot_topo_ai (h3, J_rcn, ai_res, 'residual');
```


In the figure above, we show the estimated measurand, i.e. the estimated difference topography and the ground truth difference topography used to generate the measurements. The remaining residual arises due to the fact that for estimating the difference topography we have chosen $z=0$, which is different to the ground truth (depending on the case).

Execute : Plot estimated parameter vs. ground truth

```
function plot_parameter (a_h, a_ix, a_par, a_par_gt, a_legendcellstr, a_title)
    scatter (a_h{1}, round(a_ix), a_par, 'bx'); hold (a_h{1}, 'on');
    scatter (a_h{1}, round(a_ix), a_par_gt, 'ro'); hold (a_h{1}, 'off');
    legend (a_h{1}, a_legendcellstr);
    xlabel (a_h{1}, 'index');
    ylabel (a_h{1}, 'parameter value / m');
    title (a_h{1}, a_title);
    xlim (a_h{1}, [0, max(a_ix)+1]);

    scatter (a_h{2}, round(a_ix), a_par-a_par_gt, 'gx');
    xlabel (a_h{2}, 'index');
    ylabel (a_h{2}, ' residual / m');
    title (a_h{2}, sprintf ('residual (%s)', a_title));
    xlim (a_h{2}, [0, max(a_ix)+1]);

end

fig1 = figure;
fig1.Position = [0 0 1920 1080];
h12{1} = subplot (2,2,1,'parent', fig1);
h22{1} = subplot (2,2,2,'parent', fig1);
h12{2} = subplot (2,2,3,'parent', fig1);
h22{2} = subplot (2,2,4,'parent', fig1);
plot_parameter (h12, xy_key, hat_y_1(ix_xy), y_ground_truth(ix_xy), {'xy parameter', 'ground
truth'}, 'Sut pos.')
plot_parameter (h22, ai_key, hat_y_1(ix_ai), y_ground_truth(ix_ai), {'estimated zernike',
'ground truth'}, 'Zernike coefficient')
plot_parameter (h22, ai_key, hat_y_1(ix_ai), y_ground_truth(ix_ai), {'estimated zernike',
'ground truth'}, 'Zernike coefficient')
```

```
plot_parameter (h22, ai_key, hat_y_1(ix_ai), y_ground_truth(ix_ai), {'estimated zernike',
'ground truth'}, 'Zernike coefficient')
```


Residual

```

rsd = OPDD - A_Y*hat_y_1;

A_opl_sut = J_SUT.jac_opl;
n_rays = size(A_opl_sut(:,3),1);
R = sparse(1:n_rays, 1:n_rays, A_opl_sut(:,3)); % diagonal matrix
dZ = R*rsd;

plot_ccd_fwd(J, rsd);

```


The image above shows the resulting residuals when comparing the measurement OPDDs and the generated OPDDs using the estimated parameter \hat{y} . It can be seen that the deviations compare to the assumed standard deviation of the Gaussian noise $\sigma = 10$ nm.

Saving Workspace

```
% saving Workspace
fn_name_vexp = "workspace_virtexp.mat";
save_workspace_mlx(PATH_DATA, fn_name_vexp);
```

```
saving workspace (fwd): ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1__M_Real_1__M_nom/workspace_virtexp.mat ...done (105.818s).
```

Uncertainty evaluation methods according state of the art (sota)

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Conclusion

Preliminary remarks

The following development implements a **simplified**, i.e., linearized variant of the tilted-wave interferometer (TWI) and provides uncertainty evaluation for this simplified model. Moreover, important concepts, such as model correction and post-processing of the form reconstruction result obtained (reconstruction of higher spatial frequencies and position and orientation correction of the surface under test) are not performed in this study. This means, the measurand of this simplified model differs from the measurand of the real TWI, and **the results obtained here are not representative for the quality of the actual TWI** and the obtained uncertainties may differ significantly to those obtained in the real experiment. It is to note that here and in the following, when referring to the TWI, the simplified and linearized version is considered.

Introduction

In this notebook, a benchmark scenario is developed that applies the concepts of the simplified TWI in a simple and numerically efficient way to define a virtual experiment. For that, a linearization of the TWI is considered that has been generated from analytical and numerical derivatives of the actual TWI simulation model. The combination of this linear simulation (or forward) model with a simple additive Gaussian noise assumption, provides the virtual experiment under consideration for this task.

Subsequently, several uncertainty estimation methods are implemented and applied for this specific virtual experiment and two different measurement models. Several cases are distinguished that consider different uncertainties of the input parameters.

The virtual experiment (VE) for the benchmark scenario

please refer to *run_fwd.mLx*

```

%% setting Environment
clear all;
addpath ('HELPERS');

N_mc = 1e4; % Number of Monte Carlo Runs
fprintf ('\n=====
(N_mc=%d)\n=====
\n Execution at "%s"
(N_mc=%d)\n=====
\n', string(datetime), N_mc);

=====
Execution at "09-Apr-2026 11:05:55" (N_mc=10000)
=====

```

```

specimen_id = 1;
PATH_DATA = get_path_data (specimen_id);

fn_name_vexp = fullfile (PATH_DATA, "workspace_virtexp.mat");
h_time_load = tic;
fprintf ('loading forward experiment: "%s"', fn_name_vexp);

```

loading forward experiment: "./DATA/C_8000_Real_1__M_Real_1__M_nom/workspace_virtexp.mat"

```

load (fn_name_vexp);
fprintf ('done (%gs)', toc(h_time_load));

```

done (22.9365s)

Commonly used methods for uncertainty evaluation

Law of propagation of uncertainties (LPU) using data analysis (DA)

This uncertainty evaluation method does not use the VE explicitly, but it may have been used to identify and validate the input quantities and their attributed uncertainty.

The method computes the covariance of the measurand using the law of propagation of uncertainties. For this, the input covariance needs to be defined. In our case, we set

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} U_X & 0 \\ 0 & U_Z \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then, the covariance of the measurand is given by

$$U_Y = J_f U J_f^T$$

where J_f is the derivative of the corresponding measurement model with respect to the measurand and U_f denotes the sub-matrix of U that contains all uncertainties considered in the current measurement model.

For this demonstration, we employ two different measurement models. On the one hand, we take the same model function as in the previous document on the definition of the forward experiment

$$Y_1 = f_1(X, Z) = A_Y^+(X - A_Z Z).$$

where A_Y^+ is the pseudo-inverse of the matrix A_Y used in the forward model

$$x^{\text{ve}} = A_Y y + A_Z z + \epsilon.$$

For details, cf. the previous live script corresponding the forward model and the virtual experiment.

On the other hand, we define a simplified measurement model that (naively) ignores the contribution in the additional parameters Z by fixing the value for $z = 0$. In this case the measurement model is given by

$$Y_2 = f_2(X, Z) = f_2(X) = A_Y^+(X).$$

By denoting the pseudo-inverse of A_Y by $A_Y^+ = (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} A_Y^T$, it follows that

- $J_{f_1} = [A_Y^+ \quad -A_Y^+ A_Z]$ and $U_f = \text{diag}(U_X, U_Z)$
- $J_{f_2} = [A_Y^+]$ and $U_f = U_X$

Execute : LPU using DA

```
function plot_unc_errorbar (a_h, a_ix, a_est, a_std, a_groundtruth, a_title)
    errorbar(a_h, a_ix, a_est, a_std, "-
s", "MarkerSize", 5, "MarkerEdgeColor", "blue", "MarkerFaceColor", [0.65 0.85 0.90], 'LineStyle',
'none');
    hold (a_h, 'on');
    scatter (a_h, a_ix, a_groundtruth, 'ro');
    hold (a_h, 'off');
    set (a_h, 'FontSize', 11);
    xlim (a_h, [0, max(a_ix)+1]);
    legend (a_h, {'estimated coefficients', 'ground truth'});
    xlabel (a_h, 'index');
    ylabel (a_h, 'parameter value / m');
    title (a_h, a_title);
end

% Definition of f2. Commonly used methods for uncertainty evaluation
% f1 and hat_y_1 is already defined and saved in run_fwd_ve.
f2 = @(x_) A_Y_p*(x_); %
% execute f2
hat_y_2 = f2(OPDD);

U_X = sigma^2 * speye (size (OPDD,1));
U_Z = diag (J.get_U).^2;

U_Y_1 = A_Y_p*U_X*A_Y_p' + A_Y_p*A_Z*U_Z*A_Z' *A_Y_p';
U_Y_2 = A_Y_p*U_X*A_Y_p';

fig2 = figure;
fig2.Position = [0, 0, 1980, 1024];

h1 = subplot (2,2,1,'parent', fig2);
plot_unc_errorbar (h1, xy_key, hat_y_1(ix_xy), 2*sqrt(diag(U_Y_1(ix_xy,ix_xy))),
y_ground_truth(ix_xy), 'SUT pos. (f1)');
```

```

h2 = subplot (2,2,2,'parent', fig2);
plot_unc_errorbar (h2, xy_key, hat_y_2(ix_xy), 2*sqrt(diag(U_Y_2(ix_xy,ix_xy))),
y_ground_truth(ix_xy), 'SUT pos. (f2)');

h3 = subplot (2,2,3,'parent', fig2);
plot_unc_errorbar (h3, ai_key, hat_y_1(ix_ai), 2*sqrt(diag(U_Y_1(ix_ai,ix_ai))),
y_ground_truth(ix_ai), 'zernike (f1)');

h4 = subplot (2,2,4,'parent', fig2);
plot_unc_errorbar (h4, ai_key, hat_y_2(ix_ai), 2*sqrt(diag(U_Y_2(ix_ai,ix_ai))),
y_ground_truth(ix_ai), 'zernike (f2)');

```


In this figure the resulting estimates and expanded uncertainties with $k=2$ from the two measurement models are compared to the ground-truth values considered for this example. It can directly be seen that the uncertainties resulting from the measurement model f_2 are much smaller than from using f_1 , which is clear due to the missing influence of the Z parameter

```

fig21 = figure;
fig21.Position = [0, 0, 1980, 1024];
h1 = subplot (1,2,1, 'Parent', fig21);
h2 = subplot (1,2,2, 'Parent', fig21);
fontsize = 14;
h1.XLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h1.YLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h2.XLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h2.YLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_Y_1(ix_ai,ix_ai),[]);
plot_topo_xyz (h1, p_ncy, 'Uncertainty LPU->DA, (f1)');
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_Y_2(ix_ai,ix_ai),[]);

```

```
plot_topo_xyz (h2, p_ncy, 'Uncertainty LPU->DA, (f2)');
```


Pixel-wise uncertainty resulting from the uncertainty evaluation method above (LPU applied to the DA). On the left, measurement model f_1 is used and on the right result for f_2 is presented.

```
TABLE_LPU_xy = table (hat_y_1(ix_xy), hat_y_2(ix_xy), sqrt(diag(U_Y_1(ix_xy, ix_xy))),
sqrt(diag(U_Y_2(ix_xy, ix_xy))));
TABLE_LPU_xy.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f2 est. (Sut pos. x,y)
/ m', 'f1 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f2 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m'};
TABLE_LPU_xy
```

TABLE_LPU_xy = 2x4 table

	f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	f2 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	...
1	2.5098e-06	2.5098e-06	
2	8.0112e-07	8.0112e-07	

```
TABLE_LPU_ai = table (hat_y_1(ix_ai), hat_y_2(ix_ai), sqrt(diag(U_Y_1(ix_ai,ix_ai))),
sqrt(diag(U_Y_2(ix_ai,ix_ai))));
TABLE_LPU_ai.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (ai) / m', 'f2 est.(ai) / m', 'f1 std.(ai) /
m', 'f2 std.(ai) / m'};
TABLE_LPU_ai(1:10, :)
```

ans = 10x4 table

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f2 est.(ai) / m	f1 std.(ai) / m	...
1	-2.1157e-08	-2.1157e-08	1.3560e-08	
2	2.9895e-07	2.9895e-07	1.0993e-07	
3	4.2153e-08	4.2153e-08	1.2676e-08	
4	8.7771e-09	8.7771e-09	2.1293e-09	
5	-9.5102e-09	-9.5102e-09	7.5427e-10	

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f2 est.(ai) / m	f1 std.(ai) / m	...
6	4.4224e-09	4.4224e-09	3.8017e-11	
7	-9.3846e-09	-9.3846e-09	3.6509e-11	
8	3.1672e-09	3.1672e-09	8.3090e-10	
9	-1.3383e-08	-1.3383e-08	1.1398e-09	
10	3.3962e-08	3.3962e-08	1.2030e-08	

It can be seen, that the measurement model f_2 , which ignores the uncertainty in the Z parameters generates a much smaller uncertainty in the considered coefficients, which also does not cover the true value of some of the parameters.

On the other hand, using the uncertainty of the Z parameters, the uncertainty of the considered coefficients is much larger, but covers the ground truth values.

Law of propagation of uncertainties (LPU) using the virtual experiment (VE)

In these approaches, only the VE is considered instead of the measurement model. For the *linear weighted least-squares* approach, the variability in the Z parameters is ignored and the resulting covariance reads as follows

$$U_{Y_1} = (J_Y^T U_X^{-1} J_Y)^{-1} = (A_Y^T U_X^{-1} A_Y)^{-1}$$

where J_Y denotes the Jacobian of the VE with respect to the measurand and the second equality follows due to our considered VE in (1), i.e., it holds $J_Y = A_Y$. Then, the following formula for the covariance of the measurand follows from matrix algebra and the properties of the pseudo-inverse in this case

$$\begin{aligned} U_{Y_1} &= (A_Y^T U_X^{-1} A_Y)^{-1} = ((A_Y A_Y^+ A_Y)^T U_X^{-1} A_Y A_Y^+ A_Y)^{-1} = ((A_Y (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} A_Y^T A_Y)^T U_X^{-1} A_Y (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} \\ &= (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} ((A_Y (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1})^T U_X^{-1} A_Y (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1})^{-1} (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} = A_Y^+ U_X (A_Y^+)^T \end{aligned}$$

which is equivalent to the result of the previous section using the measurement model f_2 .

At the same time, the approach following the implicit function theorem is based on the formulation of the implicit function

$$h(X, Y, Z) = Y - A_Y^+ X - A_Y^+ A_Z Z$$

and covariance of the measurand can be derived using the corresponding partial derivatives, i.e. $J_Y = I$ denoting the derivative of h with respect to the measurand and $J_{X,Z} = [-A_Y^+ \quad -A_Y^+ A_Z]$ denotes the matrix comprising the derivatives of h with respect to X and Z . Then it follows

$$U_{Y_2} = J_Y^{-1} J_{X,Z} U J_{X,Z}^T J_Y^{-T} = A_Y^+ U_X (A_Y^+)^T + A_Y^+ A_Z U_Z A_Z^T (A_Y^+)^T$$

which is again equivalent to the first approach of the previous section using the measurement model f_1 .

Propagation of distribution (PoD) applied to the data analysis (DA)

In this section, the propagation of distribution (PoD) approach using the measurement model is considered. This approach generates a probability density function for the measurand \mathcal{Y} using the following algorithm

- For $i=1,\dots,N$
- $\epsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I)$
- Draw a z_i according to assumed covariance U_i
- Generate disturbed data $\tilde{x} = X - A_z z_i + \epsilon_i$
- Compute $y_i = f(\tilde{x}, z_i)$
- Summarize sample y_1, \dots, y_n

Execute : PoD applied to DA

```

% y1_list_xy = zeros (N_mc,n_xy);
% y2_list_xy = zeros (N_mc,n_xy);
% y1_list_ai = zeros (N_mc,n_ai);
% y2_list_ai = zeros (N_mc,n_ai);

n_worker = 50;
% Do not perform Monte Carlo using for-loop. Use Matrix algebra.
zi_list = zeros(size(J.get_par('z'),1), N_mc);
for lia=1:N_mc
    J.set_par_U_rand;
    zi_list(:, lia) = J.get_par('z');
end
xi_da_list = OPDD-A_Z*zi_list + randn(size(OPDD,1),N_mc)*sigma;
y1_list_i = A_Y_p*(xi_da_list - A_Z*zi_list);
y1_list_xy = y1_list_i(ix_xy, :);
y1_list_ai = y1_list_i(ix_ai, :);

y2_list_i = A_Y_p * xi_da_list;
y2_list_xy = y2_list_i(ix_xy, :);
y2_list_ai = y2_list_i(ix_ai, :);

% for i=1:N_mc
%     epsi = randn(size(OPDD))*sigma;
randn(size(dOPD))*sigma;
%     J.set_par_U_rand;
% generates a realization according to
uncertainties defined in object
%     zi = J.get_par('z');
% returns current random realization
%     xi_da = OPDD - A_Z*zi + epsi;
%     y1_list_i = f1(xi_da, zi);
%     y2_list_i = f2(xi_da);
%     y1_list_xy(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_xy);
%     y2_list_xy(i,:) = y2_list_i(ix_xy);
%
%     y1_list_ai(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_ai);
%     y2_list_ai(i,:) = y2_list_i(ix_ai);
%

```

```

% end

U_y1 = cov(y1_list_ai);
U_y2 = cov(y2_list_ai);

f1_est_ai = mean(y1_list_ai)';
f2_est_ai = mean(y2_list_ai)';
f1_std_ai = std(y1_list_ai)';
f2_std_ai = std(y2_list_ai)';

f1_est_xy = mean(y1_list_xy)';
f2_est_xy = mean(y2_list_xy)';
f1_std_xy = std(y1_list_xy)';
f2_std_xy = std(y2_list_xy)';

fig_31 = figure;
fig_31.Position = [0 0 1920 1024];

h1 = subplot (2,2,1, 'parent', fig_31);
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_y1, []);
plot_topo_xyz (h1, p_ncy, sprintf('Uncertainty DA (f1, N=%d)', N_mc));
h2 = subplot (2,2,2, 'parent', fig_31);
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_y2, []);
plot_topo_xyz (h2, p_ncy, sprintf('Uncertainty DA (f2, N=%d)', N_mc));
h3 = subplot (2,2,3, 'parent', fig_31);
plot_topo_ai (h3, J_rcn, f1_est_ai, sprintf('Estimate DA (f1, N=%d)', N_mc));
h4 = subplot (2,2,4, 'parent', fig_31 );
plot_topo_ai (h4, J_rcn, f2_est_ai, sprintf ('Estimate DA (f2, N=%d)', N_mc));

h1.XLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h1.YLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h2.XLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h2.YLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h3.XLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h3.YLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h1.XLabel.String = "x / mm";
h2.XLabel.String = "x / mm";
h1.YLabel.String = "x / mm";
h2.YLabel.String = "x / mm";
h4.XLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h4.YLabel.FontSize = fontsize;

```


In this figure the results for the PoD applied to the DA approach are shown. The top row displays the resulting point-wise uncertainties using the measurement model f_1 (left) and the measurement model f_2 (right). The bottom row shows the resulting estimates.

It can be seen that the estimates agree well. However, the standard uncertainty is inflated on the left, compared to the right, approximately by a factor of 2.

```
function plot_histogram (a_h, a_unc_v, a_x_label, a_y_label, a_title)
    histogram (a_h, a_unc_v, 100, EdgeColor='none', Normalization = 'pdf');
    xlabel (a_h, a_x_label);
    ylabel (a_h, a_y_label);
    title (a_h, a_title);
end

fig_32 = figure;
fig_32.Position = [0 0 1920 1024];
xy_tiltes = {'SUT pos x', 'Sut pos y'};
for i=1:n_xy
    h1 = subplot (2,n_xy,i, 'parent', fig_32); % axis (h1, 'equal');
    h2 = subplot (2,n_xy,i+n_xy, 'parent', fig_32); % axis (h2, 'equal');
    if i==1
        tmp_title = 'x';
    elseif i == 2
        tmp_title = 'y';
    end

    plot_histogram (h1, y1_list_xy(:,i), sprintf('pos. deviation / m'), 'Probability density
(f1)', xy_tiltes{i});
    plot_histogram (h2, y2_list_xy(:,i), sprintf('pos. deviation / m'), 'Probability density
(f2)', xy_tiltes{i});
end
```

end

In this figure we show the resulting probability density functions (PDF) for the x- and y-position of the surface under test. These PDFs are obtained using the PoD applied to the DA approach. The top row displays the PDFs resulting from using the measurement model f_1 and the bottom row shows the PDFs resulting from using the measurement model f_2 .

Again, the PDFs are wider when using the measurement model f_2 , which indicates a larger uncertainty.

```
n_ai_5 = 5;
for i=1:n_ai_5
    h1 = subplot (2,n_ai_5,i, 'parent', fig_32); % axis (h1, 'equal');
    h2 = subplot (2,n_ai_5,i+n_ai_5, 'parent', fig_32); % axis (h2, 'equal');

    plot_histogram (h1, y1_list_ai(:,i), sprintf('zern. a_%d / m', ai_key(i)), 'Probability
density (f1)', sprintf('a_%d',ai_key(i)));
    plot_histogram (h2, y2_list_ai(:,i), sprintf('zern. a_%d / m', ai_key(i)), 'Probability
density (f2)', sprintf('a_%d',ai_key(i)));
end
```


In this figure we show the resulting PDFs for a selection of Zernike coefficients that are obtained using the approach PoD applied to the DA. Top row shows the resulting PDFs when applying the uncertainty evaluation method to the measurement model f_1 and the bottom row shows the resulting PDFs when using f_2 .

```
TABLE_POD_xy = table (f1_est_xy, f2_est_xy, f1_std_xy, f2_std_xy);
% TABLE_POD = table ('Size',[ix_end,4], 'VariableTypes', ["double", "double", "double",
"double"]);
TABLE_POD_xy.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f2 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f1 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f2 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m'};
TABLE_POD_xy
```

TABLE_POD_xy = 2x4 table

	f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	f2 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	...
1	2.5619e-06	2.5359e-06	
2	7.6162e-07	7.8137e-07	

```
TABLE_POD_ai = table (f1_est_ai, f2_est_ai, f1_std_ai, f2_std_ai);
% TABLE_POD = table ('Size',[ix_end,4], 'VariableTypes', ["double", "double", "double",
"double"]);
TABLE_POD_ai.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (ai) / m', 'f2 est. (ai) / m', 'f1 std. (ai) / m', 'f2 std. (ai) / m'};
TABLE_POD_ai(1:10, :)
```

ans = 10x4 table

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f2 est. (ai) / m	f1 std. (ai) / m	...
1	-2.1378e-08	-2.1267e-08	2.7345e-08	
2	2.9817e-07	2.9856e-07	2.1849e-07	

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f2 est. (ai) / m	f1 std. (ai) / m	...
3	4.2243e-08	4.2199e-08	2.5195e-08	
4	8.8357e-09	8.8062e-09	4.3238e-09	
5	-9.4897e-09	-9.5001e-09	1.5308e-09	
6	4.4234e-09	4.4229e-09	5.9318e-11	
7	-9.3854e-09	-9.3852e-09	3.7900e-11	
8	3.1805e-09	3.1738e-09	1.6743e-09	
9	-1.3402e-08	-1.3392e-08	2.2986e-09	
10	3.3877e-08	3.3919e-08	2.3912e-08	

Discussion of the results

It can be seen that the approach that applies the (wrong) measurement model f_2 , which ignores the contribution of the Z parameter, yields approximately the same uncertainty as the LPU applied to DA method using the (correct) measurement model f_1 .

The reason for that is that the influence of the additional Z parameter is already included in the simulation of measurement data $\tilde{x} = X - A_Z z_i + \epsilon_i$. Adding this effect again within the application of the measurement model, as is done in f_1 , counts this effect twice. This is directly visible in the approach that applies the measurement model f_1 , which yields approximately twice the uncertainty as when using f_2 . It is therefore important to analyze the effects that are applied to the input quantities X and Z , before performing a propagation through a measurement model.

Propagation of distribution (PoD) applied to the virtual experiment (VE) followed by the data analysis (DA)

In this section, the propagation of distribution (PoD) approach using the virtual experiment and the measurement model is considered. This approach generates a probability density function for the measurand Y using the following algorithm

- take a *realistic* value for the measurand y_0
- For $i=1, \dots, N$
 - draw a z_i according to assumed covariance U_z
 - apply the VE to obtain a virtual measurement $x_i^{ve} = A_Y y_0 + A_Z z_i + \epsilon_i$, where $\epsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I)$
 - $y_i = f(x_i^{ve}, z_i)$
- Summarize sample y_1, \dots, y_N

Execute: POD applied to VE followed by DA

```
% y1_list_da_xy = zeros (N_mc,n_xy);
% y2_list_da_xy = zeros (N_mc,n_xy);
%
% y1_list_da_ai = zeros (N_mc,n_ai);
% y2_list_da_ai = zeros (N_mc,n_ai);
```

```

y0 = y_ground_truth + randn(size(y_ground_truth)).*sqrt(diag(U_Y_2));

% Do not perform Monte Carlo using for-loop. Use Matrix algebra.
zi_list = zeros(size(J.get_par('z'),1), N_mc);
for lia=1:N_mc
    J.set_par_U_rand;
    zi_list(:, lia) = J.get_par('z');
end
xi_ve_list = A_Y*y0 + A_Z*zi_list + randn(size(OPDD,1),N_mc)*sigma;
y1_list_i = A_Y_p*(xi_ve_list - A_Z*zi_list);
y1_list_da_xy = y1_list_i(ix_xy, :);
y1_list_da_ai = y1_list_i(ix_ai, :);

y2_list_i = A_Y_p * xi_da_list;
y2_list_da_xy = y2_list_i(ix_xy, :);
y2_list_da_ai = y2_list_i(ix_ai, :);

% open_parallel_pool (n_worker);
% for i=1:N_mc
%     epsi = randn(size(OPDD))*sigma;
%     J.set_par_U_rand; % generates a realization according to
uncertainties defined in object % returns current random realization
%     zi = J.get_par('z');
%     xi_ve = A_Y*y0 + A_Z*zi + epsi;
%     y1_list_i = f1(xi_ve, zi);
%     y2_list_i = f2(xi_ve);
%     y1_list_da_xy(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_xy);
%     y2_list_da_xy(i,:) = y2_list_i(ix_xy);
%     y1_list_da_ai(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_ai);
%     y2_list_da_ai(i,:) = y2_list_i(ix_ai);
% end

f1_est_xy = mean(y1_list_da_xy)';
f2_est_xy = mean(y2_list_da_xy)';
f1_std_xy = std(y1_list_da_xy)';
f2_std_xy = std(y2_list_da_xy)';

f1_est_ai = mean(y1_list_da_ai)';
f2_est_ai = mean(y2_list_da_ai)';
f1_std_ai = std(y1_list_da_ai)';
f2_std_ai = std(y2_list_da_ai)';

U_y1 = cov([y1_list_da_xy y1_list_da_ai]);
U_y2 = cov([y2_list_da_xy y2_list_da_ai]);

fig_41 = figure;
fig_41.Position = [0 0 1920 1024];
h1 = subplot (2,2,1, 'parent', fig_41);
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_y1(ix_ai, ix_ai), []);
plot_topo_xyz (h1, p_ncy, sprintf ('Uncertainty POD_{VE} (f1, N=%d)', N_mc));

```

```

h2 = subplot (2, 2,2, 'parent', fig_41);
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_y2(ix_ai, ix_ai), []);
plot_topo_xyz (h2, p_ncy, sprintf ('Uncertainty POD_{VE} (f2, N=%d)', N_mc));
h3 = subplot (2,2,3, 'parent', fig_41);
plot_topo_ai (h3, J_rcn, f1_est_ai, sprintf ('Estimate POD_{VE} (f1, N=%d)', N_mc));
h4 = subplot (2,2,4, 'parent', fig_41);
plot_topo_ai (h4, J_rcn, f2_est_ai, sprintf ('Estimate POD_{VE} (f2, N=%d)', N_mc));
h1.XLabel.String = "x / mm";
h1.YLabel.String = "x / mm";
h2.XLabel.String = "x / mm";
h2.YLabel.String = "x / mm";
h1.XLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h1.YLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h2.XLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h2.YLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h3.XLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h3.YLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h4.XLabel.FontSize = fontsize;
h4.YLabel.FontSize = fontsize;

```


In this figure we show the results that are obtained by applying the PoD applied to the VE approach. The top row shows the point-wise standard uncertainty and the bottom row shows the resulting estimates. On the left, the measurement model f_1 is used and on the right, the measurement model f_2 is employed.

Both approaches yield similar estimates but using the measurement model f_1 reduces the uncertainty by multiple orders of magnitude.

```

f42 = figure;
f42.Position = [0 0 1600 1024];
xy_tiltes = {'Sut pos. x', 'Sut pos. y'};

```

```

for i=1:n_xy
    h1 = subplot (2,n_xy,i, 'parent', f42);
    h2 = subplot (2,n_xy,i+n_xy, 'parent', f42);

    plot_histogram (h1, y1_list_xy(:,i), sprintf('pos deviation / m'), 'Probability density
(f1)', xy_tiltes{i});
    plot_histogram (h2, y2_list_xy(:,i), sprintf('pos deviation / m'), 'Probability density
(f2)', xy_tiltes{i});

end

```


In this figure we show the resulting probability density functions (PDF) for the x- and y-position of the surface under test. These PDFs are obtained using the PoD applied to the DA approach. The top row displays the PDFs resulting from using the measurement model f_1 and the bottom row shows the PDFs resulting from using the measurement model f_2 .

```

fig_43 = figure;
fig_43.Position = [0 0 1920 1024];

for i=1:n_ai_5
    h1 = subplot (2,n_ai_5,i, 'parent', fig_43); % axis (h1, 'equal');
    h2 = subplot (2,n_ai_5,i+n_ai_5, 'parent', fig_43); % axis (h2, 'equal');

    plot_histogram (h1, y1_list_da_ai(:,i), sprintf('a_%d / m', ai_key(i)), 'Probability
density (f1)', sprintf('a_%d',ai_key(i)));

```

```

plot_histogram (h2, y2_list_da_ai(:,i), sprintf('a_%d / m', ai_key(i)), 'Probability
density (f2)', sprintf('a_%d',ai_key(i)));
end

```


In this figure we show the resulting PDFs for a selection of Zernike coefficients that are obtained using the approach PoD applied to the DA. Top row shows the resulting PDFs when applying the uncertainty evaluation method to the measurement model f_1 and the bottom row shows the resulting PDFs when using f_2 .

```

TABLE_POD_VE_xy = table (f1_est_xy, f2_est_xy, f1_std_xy, f2_std_xy);
TABLE_POD_VE_xy.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m ', 'f2 est. (Sut pos.
x,y) / m ', 'f1 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m ', 'f2 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m '};
TABLE_POD_VE_xy

```

TABLE_POD_VE_xy = 2x4 table

	f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	f2 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	...
1	-3.0257e-08	2.5359e-06	
2	-3.9886e-08	7.8137e-07	

```

TABLE_POD_VE_ai = table (f1_est_ai, f2_est_ai, f1_std_ai, f2_std_ai);
TABLE_POD_VE_ai.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (ai) / m ', 'f2 est. (ai) / m ', 'f1 std.
(ai) / m ', 'f2 std. (ai) / m '};
TABLE_POD_VE_ai(1:10, :)

```

ans = 10x4 table

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f2 est. (ai) / m	f1 std. (ai) / m	...
1	-4.2395e-09	-2.1267e-08	3.7490e-11	
2	4.3333e-07	2.9856e-07	2.3296e-11	

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f2 est. (ai) / m	f1 std. (ai) / m	...
3	2.6588e-08	4.2199e-08	4.0890e-11	
4	1.0078e-08	8.8062e-09	3.9754e-11	
5	-9.0063e-09	-9.5001e-09	3.4255e-11	
6	4.3756e-09	4.4229e-09	2.7715e-11	
7	-9.3536e-09	-9.3852e-09	3.5729e-11	
8	2.0980e-09	3.1738e-09	3.2006e-11	
9	-1.1967e-08	-1.3392e-08	3.0357e-11	
10	4.8709e-08	3.3919e-08	2.5161e-11	

Discussion of the results

It can be seen that this approach generates completely different uncertainties as the previous approaches. Using the measurement model f_1 results in an almost negligible uncertainty, which is due to the fact that the double use of the uncertainty in the Z parameter (once in the input quantity and once in the measurement model) cancels. Also when using f_2 , and in contrast to the previous approaches, there is a larger uncertainty remaining, which is generated by the specific choice of a simulated value y_0 for the measurand, which may be different to the true value of the measurand that is usually unknown.

Further results of this approach using measurement model f1

Position parameter (xy) estimate

```
TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_est = table (TABLE_LPU_xy(:,1).Variables, TABLE_LPU_xy(:,1).Variables,
TABLE_POD_xy(:,1).Variables, TABLE_POD_VE_xy(:,1).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_est.Properties.VariableNames = {'LPU->DA (est.) / m', 'LPU->VE (est.) / m',
'POD->DA (est.) / m', 'POD: LPU->VE (est.) / m'};
TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_est
```

TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_est = 2x4 table

	LPU->DA (est.) / m	LPU->VE (est.) / m	POD->DA (est.) / m	...
1	2.5098e-06	2.5098e-06	2.5619e-06	
2	8.0112e-07	8.0112e-07	7.6162e-07	

Position parameter (xy) standard deviation

```
TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_std = table (TABLE_LPU_xy(:,3).Variables, TABLE_LPU_xy(:,3).Variables,
TABLE_POD_xy(:,3).Variables, TABLE_POD_VE_xy(:,3).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_std.Properties.VariableNames = {'std: LPU->DA (std.) / m', 'LPU->VE (std.)
/ m', 'POD->DA (std.) / m', 'POD: LPU->VE (std.) / m'};
TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_std
```

TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_std = 2x4 table

	std: LPU->DA (std.) / m	LPU->VE (std.) / m	...
1	1.4849e-06	1.4849e-06	
2	1.4270e-06	1.4270e-06	

Zernike parameter (ai) estimate

```
TABLE_RESULT_F1_ai_est = table (TABLE_LPU_ai(:,1).Variables, TABLE_LPU_ai(:,1).Variables,
TABLE_POD_ai(:,1).Variables, TABLE_POD_VE_ai(:,1).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_F1_ai_est.Properties.VariableNames = {'LPU->DA (est.) / m', 'LPU->VE (est.) / m',
'POD->DA (est.) / m', 'POD: LPU->VE (est.) / m'};
TABLE_RESULT_F1_ai_est(1:10, :)
```

ans = 10×4 table

	LPU->DA (est.) / m	LPU->VE (est.) / m	POD->DA (est.) / m	...
1	-2.1157e-08	-2.1157e-08	-2.1378e-08	
2	2.9895e-07	2.9895e-07	2.9817e-07	
3	4.2153e-08	4.2153e-08	4.2243e-08	
4	8.7771e-09	8.7771e-09	8.8357e-09	
5	-9.5102e-09	-9.5102e-09	-9.4897e-09	
6	4.4224e-09	4.4224e-09	4.4234e-09	
7	-9.3846e-09	-9.3846e-09	-9.3854e-09	
8	3.1672e-09	3.1672e-09	3.1805e-09	
9	-1.3383e-08	-1.3383e-08	-1.3402e-08	
10	3.3962e-08	3.3962e-08	3.3877e-08	

Zernike parameter (ai) standard deviation

```
TABLE_RESULT_F1_ai_std = table (TABLE_LPU_ai(:,3).Variables, TABLE_LPU_ai(:,3).Variables,
TABLE_POD_ai(:,3).Variables, TABLE_POD_VE_ai(:,3).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_F1_ai_std.Properties.VariableNames = {'std: LPU->DA (std.) / m', 'LPU->VE (std.)
/ m', 'POD->DA (std.) / m', 'POD: LPU->VE (std.) / m'};
TABLE_RESULT_F1_ai_std(1:10, :)
```

ans = 10×4 table

	std: LPU->DA (std.) / m	LPU->VE (std.) / m	...
1	1.3560e-08	1.3560e-08	
2	1.0993e-07	1.0993e-07	
3	1.2676e-08	1.2676e-08	
4	2.1293e-09	2.1293e-09	
5	7.5427e-10	7.5427e-10	
6	3.8017e-11	3.8017e-11	
7	3.6509e-11	3.6509e-11	
8	8.3090e-10	8.3090e-10	
9	1.1398e-09	1.1398e-09	
10	1.2030e-08	1.2030e-08	

Further results of this approach using measurement model f2

Position parameter (xy) estimate

```
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_est = table (TABLE_LPU_xy(:,2).Variables, TABLE_LPU_xy(:,2).Variables,  
TABLE_POD_xy(:,2).Variables, TABLE_POD_VE_xy(:,2).Variables);  
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_est.Properties.VariableNames = ["LPU->DA (est.) / m", "LPU->VE (est.) / m",  
"POD->DA (est.) / m", "POD: LPU->VE (est.) / m"];  
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_est
```

TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_est = 2x4 table

	LPU->DA (est.) / m	LPU->VE (est.) / m	POD->DA (est.) / m	...
1	2.5098e-06	2.5098e-06	2.5359e-06	
2	8.0112e-07	8.0112e-07	7.8137e-07	

Position parameter (xy) standard deviation

```
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_std = table (TABLE_LPU_xy(:,4).Variables, TABLE_LPU_xy(:,4).Variables,  
TABLE_POD_xy(:,4).Variables, TABLE_POD_VE_xy(:,4).Variables);  
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_std.Properties.VariableNames = ["LPU->DA (std.) / m", "LPU->VE (std.) /  
m", "POD->DA (std.) / m", "POD: LPU->VE (std.) / m"];  
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_std
```

TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_std = 2x4 table

	LPU->DA (std.) / m	LPU->VE (std.) / m	POD->DA (std.) / m	...
1	6.3585e-11	6.3585e-11	1.4938e-06	
2	7.0297e-11	7.0297e-11	1.4492e-06	

Zernike parameter (ai) estimate

```
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_est = table (TABLE_LPU_ai(:,2).Variables, TABLE_LPU_ai(:,2).Variables,  
TABLE_POD_ai(:,2).Variables, TABLE_POD_VE_ai(:,2).Variables);  
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_est.Properties.VariableNames = ["LPU->DA (est.) / m", "LPU->VE (est.) / m",  
"POD->DA (est.) / m", "POD: LPU->VE (est.) / m"];  
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_est(1:10, :)
```

ans = 10x4 table

	LPU->DA (est.) / m	LPU->VE (est.) / m	POD->DA (est.) / m	...
1	-2.1157e-08	-2.1157e-08	-2.1267e-08	
2	2.9895e-07	2.9895e-07	2.9856e-07	
3	4.2153e-08	4.2153e-08	4.2199e-08	
4	8.7771e-09	8.7771e-09	8.8062e-09	
5	-9.5102e-09	-9.5102e-09	-9.5001e-09	
6	4.4224e-09	4.4224e-09	4.4229e-09	
7	-9.3846e-09	-9.3846e-09	-9.3852e-09	
8	3.1672e-09	3.1672e-09	3.1738e-09	
9	-1.3383e-08	-1.3383e-08	-1.3392e-08	

	LPU->DA (est.) / m	LPU->VE (est.) / m	POD->DA (est.) / m	...
10	3.3962e-08	3.3962e-08	3.3919e-08	

Zernike parameter (ai) standard deviation

```
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_std = table (TABLE_LPU_ai(:,4).Variables, TABLE_LPU_ai(:,4).Variables,
TABLE_POD_ai(:,4).Variables, TABLE_POD_VE_ai(:,4).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_std.Properties.VariableNames = ["LPU->DA (std.) / m", "LPU->VE (std.) /
m", "POD->DA (std.) / m", "POD: LPU->VE (std.) / m"];
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_std(1:10, :)
```

ans = 10x4 table

	LPU->DA (std.) / m	LPU->VE (std.) / m	POD->DA (std.) / m	...
1	3.7592e-11	3.7592e-11	1.3673e-08	
2	2.3484e-11	2.3484e-11	1.0925e-07	
3	4.1472e-11	4.1472e-11	1.2597e-08	
4	3.9662e-11	3.9662e-11	2.1618e-09	
5	3.4602e-11	3.4602e-11	7.6593e-10	
6	2.7652e-11	2.7652e-11	3.8099e-11	
7	3.5831e-11	3.5831e-11	3.5901e-11	
8	3.1874e-11	3.1874e-11	8.3741e-10	
9	2.9945e-11	2.9945e-11	1.1499e-09	
10	2.4838e-11	2.4838e-11	1.1956e-08	

Conclusion

In this work, a benchmark scenario for a (simplified) TWI has been developed and several uncertainty evaluation methods have been implemented for this benchmark scenario and two different choices of measurement models were analyzed. Hereby, the uncertainty resulting from the first approach (Linear Propagation of Uncertainty (LPU) applied to Data Analysis (DA)) using the measurement model f_1 serves as the reference, assuming that f_1 is known and represents the correct measurement model.

It has been shown that the method LPU applied to the VE is equivalent to the Propagation of Distribution (PoD) method applied to the DA, due to the linearity of the VE and the chosen measurement models.

For the Monte Carlo sampling procedures, i.e. the PoD methods, the results show that the measurement model f_2 yields results much closer to the reference, than using the measurement model f_1 , which has been assumed to be the correct one. This behavior can be explained analytically due to the linearity assumptions made and the inclusion of the uncertainty of quantities with type B information is already done while sampling from the input quantities.

Algorithm 2 (MC-VE) Virtual Experiment Monte Carlo algorithm

Input: VE as in (1), real observations $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_m$, state-of-knowledge PDF $\pi(z)$, number of samples of measurand N , simulated value of measurand y_0 , covariance used in virtual experiment $\Sigma = \text{diag}(\sigma_1^2, \dots, \sigma_n^2)$.

Output: Samples from state-of-knowledge PDF of measurand $\pi(y)$ with the same mean and covariance estimate as in algorithm 1.

- 1: Estimate experimental mean vector \bar{x} and scaled experimental covariance S as given in (8)
- 2: $LL^T = S/m \leftarrow$ compute Cholesky decomposition of S/m
- 3: for $i = 1, \dots, N$ do
- 4: $z'_i \leftarrow$ Draw sample from PDF $\pi(z)$
- 5: $\bar{x}_i^{ve} \leftarrow$ experimental mean of m virtual experiment realizations

$$\bar{x}_i^{ve} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m G(y_0, z'_i, \epsilon_j) \quad (14)$$

- 6: $\mu_i \leftarrow$ get mean estimate from virtual experiment according to (12)
- 7: $J_i \leftarrow$ get gradient estimate from virtual experiment according to (13)
- 8: $c_i \leftarrow$ sample a single realization from a χ^2 distribution with $\nu = m - n$ degrees of freedom
- 9: $T_i \leftarrow$ create transformation matrix to correct for unknown variances according to (9)

$$T_i = L \text{diag} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\nu m}}{\sigma_1 \sqrt{c_i}}, \dots, \frac{\sqrt{\nu m}}{\sigma_n \sqrt{c_i}} \right) \quad (15)$$

- 10: $y'_i \leftarrow$ obtain corrected sample from desired PDF by

$$y'_i = J_i^{-1} (T_i(\mu_i - \bar{x}_i^{ve}) + (\bar{x} - \mu_i)) + y_0, \quad (16)$$

where J_i^{-1} denotes the left (pseudo) inverse of J_i .

- 11: end for
- 12: Summarize samples y'_1, \dots, y'_N to obtain estimate and uncertainty in terms of mean and covariance matrix

$$\hat{y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y'_i, \quad U_Y = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (y'_i - \hat{y})(y'_i - \hat{y})^T. \quad (17)$$

- 13: The standard uncertainty of every element of Y is given by the square-root of the diagonal elements of U_Y .
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